

VALKYRIES

D6.6 Harmonisation opportunities on the preparedness and cross- sectorial collaboration for first aid response to multi-casualty disasters M18

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1. Executive Summary

This document presents a report about analysis of the required capabilities/needs identification and gaps in the field of crisis management concerning First Aid Responders (FARs), crisis managers, volunteers and other humanitarian actors.

This deliverable D6.6 is an update of the previously submitted document D6.2 – Harmonisation opportunities on the preparedness and cross-sectorial collaboration for first aid response to multi-casualty disasters – A/1. The general updates at the WP6 level and the specific updates at the tasks level are summarised in the Introduction section. In addition, the new content with respect to the last version submitted has been highlighted in yellow for easy review and identification

The gathered information is based on different resources such as literature reviews, document analysis, professional experience, surveys, etc. Based on the analysis of the existing capabilities, presented in D6.5, the required capabilities and needs for FARs at the national and the EU level in case of cross-border Mass Casualty Incidents (MCI) are described and divided into different categories for facilitation of the explanation: technological, material, human, organisational, etc.).

The structure of the report also includes an analysis of gaps which covers topics as coordination issues among the responsible/leading organisations providing training, lack of harmonisation among existing training courses, their content and focus, as well as participants, limited capabilities that first responders have in terms of cross-border emergency data federation, lack of protocols for coordination between military and civil actors, etc.

Based on the analysis of the identified gaps, harmonization opportunities on the preparedness and cross-sectorial collaboration for first aid response to multi-casualty disasters are proposed.

Besides, the document summarises the results from the studies carried out in the framework of the T.6.1 Resource Federation and trusted information sharing, T6.2 Education and Training for first aid responses, T6.3 Raising practitioner and social awareness, T6.4 Civil-Military Cooperation and T6.5 Civil Protection and Aid Volunteerism.

Finally, the deliverable presents some conclusions and recommendations.

2. Identification

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3. Introduction

The goal of this report is to provide an analysis of the required capabilities/needs identification and gaps, as well as harmonisation opportunities in the field of crisis management concerning First Aid Responders (FARs) and other actors in crisis management such as fire fighters, police, military, volunteers, etc. The focus is on in cross-border, cross-sectorial and cross-hierarchical context.

The report combines the results from the studies carried out in the framework of the tasks T.6.1 Resource Federation and trusted information sharing, T6.2 Education and Training for first aid responses, T6.3 Raising practitioner and social awareness, T6.4 Civil-Military Cooperation and T6.5 Civil Protection and Aid Volunteerism.

The deliverable D6.6 is an update of D6.2 version A/1.

In deliverable D6.6 the general updates at the WP6 level are related to the following. First, all partners prepared a summary of the harmonization opportunities by tasks. In addition, the number of gaps and opportunities were reviewed with the goal to cluster them and to merge the gaps and opportunities that are similar/close by meaning. Besides, some opportunities that were not related to gaps were removed. Also, gaps – opportunities identification was added to each table. Finally, WP6 conclusions section was developed.

In the following rows the specific contribution of each task to update the content of the deliverable D6.6 is presented.

Contribution from T6.1

- Improved format of the document;
- Added references missing;
- Added text related to gaps or opportunities that were missing, based on the common methodology agreed between the WPs 4, WP5 and WP6;
- Added two new opportunities: OP6.1-29 and OP6.1-30;
- Checking and ensuring that all gaps are related to at least one opportunity.

Contribution from T6.2

- Review of the format of the deliverable and improvement of the content;
- Merging some overlapping opportunities and deleting some of them that are not related to education and training of first aid responses;
- Ensuring that there is no gap/s without at least one opportunity;
- Adding gap identifications to each opportunity;
- Adding one more gap and opportunity G6.2-22: Insufficient joint multinational training for first responders and corresponding harmonization opportunity OP6.2-9: Development and testing of Joint multinational training for first responders.

Contribution from T6.3

- In D6.2 there were 8 gaps and 6 opportunities identified. In D6.2 owners of G6.3-7 and G6.3-8 did not identify related opportunities. In this D6.6 task leader and contributors to T6.3 identified 7 gaps with 7 opportunities, each opportunity comes from related gap. G6.3-7 Intentional misleading of first responders and civil protection service which was

identified as professional experience was extracted due to not matching the purpose of T6.3;

- G6.3-8 was afterwards renumbered and become G6.3-7 with the name: Lack of citizen engagement in Disaster and in risk reduction;
- Chapter 8.4 Conclusions for Raising practitioner and social awareness – this was slightly changed, since there were changes made inside chapters 6.3 and 7.3.

Contribution from T6.4

- Texts related to civil-military interaction were mainly edited and revised. In chapter 6.4 the total number of gaps has been reduced from 8 to 6 and those that have no relation with the training and preparation of the First Aid Responders or duplicate other have been dropped (G6.4-3, G6.4-2).
- Every gap has been named and edited again. In chapter 7.4 all options have been edited and reformulated again in order to improve coordination and harmonization, the total number is the same, but those that are not concerned by new gaps are removed (OP6.4-5).

Contribution from T6.5

- In the D6.6 the relation between find gaps and opportunities was better explicated and harmonized with the reduction of number of opportunities through aggregation of similar or near gap in the same opportunities group and with identification of gaps outside the project scope such as Gaps G6.5-3 and G6.5-5 that implies government involvement;
- Furthermore, the opportunities identified have been explained better and in more detail.

3.1. Methodology

The VALKYRIES project has developed a common methodology for the second deliverables (Dx.2, correspondingly Dx.6) of the work packages WP4, WP5 and WP6. It has shown the need to link deliverables so that ideas flow from the primitive state to finally become a real opportunity for project stakeholders.

In this way, no idea, gap or opportunity will go unanalysed, or its feasibility assessed.

This methodology clarifies the inputs and outputs of each of the stages defined. Particularly, it is composed of three stages, based on the pre-standardisation map designed earlier in the project, presented as follows:

- State of the art, and pre-identification of gaps.
- Gap and communalities analysis, and harmonisation opportunities.
- VALKYRIES outputs.

According with this step about **harmonisation and opportunities**, there are many benefits of having a common working methodology for the different work packages, and one of them is to be able to work not only as a unit but also as a whole.

3.1.1. Structure criteria

The common structure of these technical deliverables has been composed by these chapters:

- **Required capabilities**

This first chapter explains the capabilities required by the user in the emergency. This chapter serves as a link between the previous work about the landscape of the technical purpose of the

project, the analysis of the existing state of the art, and the analysis of surveys shared with other first responders. Based on the study of these capabilities required by users for both topic and tasks of the project, different desired capabilities could differ from those currently available. This situation creates a potential gap that will be reflected in the next chapter.

- **Identification of Gaps**

This chapter is the continuation of the pre-identified gaps in the previous work at the landscape. In particular, this section presents problems or needs of the technical topic and that limit the actuation of first responders and the capabilities of technological solutions.

Thus, this chapter has two very different parts:

- Concept development. It indicates why a situation represents a gap, what problems it causes or harmonization necessities, among other aspects.
- Summary and codification of the gaps. It contains tables that summarise the gaps previously identified to ease their review and understanding.

- **Harmonisation Opportunities**

This chapter is the output of the deliverable and the inputs for the work in the incoming months and deliverables. This section aims to determine if the previously identified gaps can be solved and, if so, how they could be solved.

As in the previous chapter, the present one has two distinct parts:

- Concept development. It presents in a detailed way the potential solutions derived from the previous gaps, the problems they cause and harmonisation necessities, among other aspects of interest.
- Summary and codification of the opportunities. It presents tables to summarise the opportunities detected.

3.1.2. ID Codification/Traceability

All the gaps and opportunities identified in the document have been assigned an identifier in order to have a traceability.

The code is created as follows:

- The 1st part of the code identifies if it is a gap or an opportunity, indicated by a G or an OP.
- The 2nd part of the code is for the task of the project that had more relationship with the gap/opportunity.
- The 3rd part of the code is just a hyphen to divide and improve legibility.
- The 4th part of the code is for the item number. This number starts from 1 to n. Any change in the first three parts of the code starts a new coding of part 4 from 1 to n.

1 st part	2 nd part	3 rd part	4 th part
G=Gap OP= Opportunity	Task number	-	Item number (1..n)
Example			
G	6.1	-	1

Table 1 – ID codification structure for traceability

Traceability is crucial in this type of methodology both for readability and for establishing a link between different work packages and deliverables. Additionally, gaps and opportunities must be identified in a useful and handy way. Only following a structured nomenclature can the items

be identified and referenced without investing too much effort. At later stages, this codification also allows to create relations between gaps and opportunities.

3.2. Exclusion criteria

There are harmonization needs (gaps and opportunities) that although related to emergency and the use cases are not part of the technical discussion.

Governance issues are outside the scope of the project. They are part of the political discussion. The project is not intended to work on these issues and therefore they are out of scope and do not appear within this deliverable.

3.3. Information source

The information collected and analysed in the report comes from different sources such as literature reviews, documentary analysis, professional experience, surveys, etc. Besides, analysis of lessons learned from previous crisis management operations were carried out to identify needs/gaps and opportunities for improving main E&T, regulatory gaps and collaboration opportunities in first aid response activities/capacities, CIMIC activities, etc.

3.4. Experts' consultation

The partners listed as contributors in WP6 developed a questionnaire to identify the gaps/needs for education, training and collaboration among the first aid responders. **The results are utilised as a source of information while defining capabilities gaps and harmonisation opportunities in this updated report. The questionnaire and the results are presented as annexes in deliverable D6.5.**

4. Required capabilities/Needs identification

4.1. Resource Federation and trusted information sharing

This section presents a description of the capabilities identified regarding resource federation and trusted information sharing. These capabilities are divided in different categories for easing their explanation, as presented in subsequent sections.

4.1.1. Data federation between organisations

Cross-border, cross-sectorial and cross-hierarchical emergency scenarios managed by first responders directly depend on an effective communication between organisations. Additionally, these scenarios generate a huge amount of information, characterised by their heterogeneity between organisations and first responder category. Based on that, data federation technologies with a dynamic behaviour are essential to ensure an effective communication and represent the particularities of these environments. Another essential characteristic of data federation technologies is the scalability of the system, which is related to its dynamic behaviour. These systems need the capability of increasing or decreasing its resources on demand to satisfy the requirements of the emergency.

Based on the above, different technologies offering data federation need to be considered and implemented in such scenarios. These technologies must be widely available, accessible, and standardised to be included in cross-border emergency scenarios. Furthermore, they require to manage the complexity of these scenarios in terms of technological capabilities.

Another relevant aspect to take into consideration is that the countries participating in the emergency have different regulations that affect the information that they can share with external entities. Thus, these scenarios require the ability to adequately share data between parties during a particular duration, with a determined granularity, and with authorisation approaches. For that, clear guidelines and regulations are necessary to have a common picture at the European level.

4.1.2. Mechanism to provide data confidentiality

During the emergency actuations, especially in cross-border cases, which involve different organizations cooperating during their actuations, the huge amount of information handled needs to accomplish certain confidentiality requirements. The information handled includes the information generated during the actuations and the required information that should be retrieved from other sources.

Multiple mechanisms can be used to provide the required data confidentiality, including libraries, standards, and approaches, such as the symmetric and asymmetric cryptography.

4.1.3. Mechanism to provide resource integrity

The integrity of the data exchanged during emergency events is a critical resource, as misinformation or poor data integrity can lead to wrongful understanding of the situation, a bias situational awareness and a poor or limited decision-making process.

These risks are highly augmented when different organizations and entities, from different background of culture, processes, and tools, are required to cooperate in cross-border events. These risks are augmented when different languages, organization structures, data topologies and units, data structures, among other elements, are merged into a common operation. These differences can lead to difficulties in generating a common understanding of the situational

awareness shared by all the entities involved. Also, the perspective of the different entities and roles leads to different data needs, and a data shared should be displayed with a clear distinction of the data origin. Decision makers should, therefore, make an assessment based on the trust of the data, including its origin, certainty that the data was not tampered, and that all required data is available and recovered, if necessary.

4.1.4. Mechanism to provide availability of the collaboration

Frameworks offering data federation platforms require a certain level of integration, permissions to handle information, partnerships with emergency responders, data security, anonymization of victims and responders. Any organisation will make its data available without first validating the framework's capabilities.

Training in the frameworks to move swiftly, provide quality and relevant information, and not provide misinform during the emergency,

For these reasons, it is complex to get organisations involved in information sharing.

Collaboration for data sharing is not very usual between organisations.

The main reasons are that it is unknown whether the organisation receiving the data will treat it appropriately. Whether it will offer minimum values of security, confidentiality and integrity. Any organisation wants its data or that of its stakeholders to be compromised by third parties.

Another reason for the lack of collaboration is the low level of integration of frameworks. In some cases, information is provided and received that is not relevant to the emergency, creating a sense of disinformation. In which the information displayed is not processed and is not really useful or understandable to the end user.

4.1.5. Frameworks offering data federation

In a cross-border multiple-casualty disaster, information sharing is vital. This need for information sharing is closely related to the sharing capabilities of technology. In developed countries, there is software that collects disaster information, which eases this process. Digitisation of member's activity and data monitoring is essential for sharing information among emergency responders.

An extra level of difficulty is added when the disaster involves different countries. This can occur for two main reasons, because the disaster is extreme and requires international collaboration or because the disaster occurs on a border. We will focus on the latter.

Anyway, an interoperability gap between different countries can be presented in the following ways:

- Digitisation of constituents
- Advancement of technology
- Language
- Institutional hierarchy
- Nature of data

In these frameworks that offer data federation capabilities the data is used for two purposes. First, the information is useful for disaster management. Secondly, in a post-emergency manner. These data are useful for analysing how emergency management has worked and moving

towards continuous improvement in data sharing systems, resource management and organisational performance.

As we have seen in previous steps of the project, there are currently different types of frameworks that offer data federation capabilities. Now, those identified by the project are:

- Insarag (International Search and Rescue Advisory Group)
- Virtual OSOCC (On-Site Operations Coordination Centre) part of the Disaster and Coordination System (GDACS)
- GAIA-X common European project
- SIRFTI (Security Incident Response Trust Framework for Federated Identity)
- BEACON common European project
- Oracle UIM federation framework
- Micro Focus federation framework

As can be seen, there are different frameworks with similar purposes. At least for the time being, there is no interoperability between the platforms. Based on that, the lack of harmonisation on this point is clear.

4.2. Education and Training for first aid responses

Cross-border Mass Casualty Incidents (MCI) involve several agencies from different countries working together.

The Education and Training (E&T) of first aid responders varies within European countries. Cross-border co-operation in MCI requires comparable knowledge bases and be able to provide equivalent services between the EU Member States (MS).

Efficiency and timeliness are crucial. This means strong preparedness by means of effective E&T.

An advanced education and training kit focused on cross-border MCI for first responders at the European level and according to national guidelines would align the different EU MS and their members would be able to work in a more effective way. This E&T kit should develop:

A) Curricula

- Knowledge and skills for measurement and registration of physiological indicators;
- Performing medical manipulations;
- Assessment of the condition and vital functions of the patients and victims;
- Emergencies requiring immediate first aid and behavioural algorithms;
- Evacuation of a victim from a dangerous area or place of an accident;
- Behaviour and activities in crisis and disaster situations.

B) Methodology of education.

- Allow blended methodology, which combines the training of theoretical contents through virtual platforms and face-to-face activities for the acquisition of practical skills.
- Use of virtual reality or mixed reality tools that simulate scenarios where competences that are difficult to obtain in real life situations can be achieved.
- Create training pathways with learning routes adapted to the different professional profiles, but common in the different EU MS.

C) Training materials.

- Interlinked digital platforms
- Dummies and high-fidelity simulation rooms.
- Audio-visual elements for the development of virtual reality or mixed reality.
- Organisational structures that allow for the development of multi-stakeholder drills

Different agencies involved in emergency response often follow an operational approach to training, immersing their teams into contexts they will likely be exposed to once in the field. Simulations, teamwork, pre-deployment preparation and the inclusion of regional and national actors are key features of their training practices.

The minimum E&T will always depend on the area and category of the professionals, and always taking into account the minimum compulsory education. The requirements would be adapted to the professional category (given the multidisciplinary nature of the professionals in the emergency service), assistants, doctors, nurses, technicians, etc.

The training should be based on different learning pathways according to the roles to perform in the emergency.

Courses should address data management needs:

- To limit the risks of the data breach (loss of data, unauthorized access, etc.) due to improper human behaviours and ineffective organizational procedures.
- To contribute to a more effective governance and management of information, by developing knowledge and digital skills of first responders.
- The first aid responders from all EU countries should react in symbiosis between each other, following the previous mentioned E&T kit and having the following skills:
- To measure and register basic physiological indicators.
- To follow the basic vital indicators.
- To recognise the symptoms of brain injuries.
- To identify breath irregularities.
- To recognise incidents caused by electricity.
- To recognise breath, heart failure and blood circulation.
- To identify bone fractures, joint and limb injuries.
- To recognise abdominal injuries.
- To recognise life-threatening bleeding.
- To identify shock condition and to apply the necessary measures for eliminating it.
- To identify the condition of hypothermia and apply the necessary measures for eliminating it.
- To make decontamination actions on the place of the incident.
- To recognise potential signals of poisoning and allergic reactions and to take the necessary measures for urgent situations connecting with severe intoxication and/or allergic reactions.
- To recognise and react in cases of acid and base burning.

4.3. Raising practitioner and social awareness

4.3.1. Introduction

Awareness can be simply defined as having or showing realization, perception or knowledge about situations with respect to conditions and circumstances, relative position or combination of circumstances at a certain moment.

For its part, situational awareness can be defined as the perception of the elements in the environment within a volume of time and space, the comprehension of their meaning, and the projection of their status in the near future.

Further specifying this definition for the concrete case of cross-sectorial and cross-border MCI in which both emergency teams from two or more countries and the population close to the event are involved, raising practitioner and social awareness implies:

- The exchange of critical information among different first aid responders;
- Generation of a public and private context for situation assessment;
- Setting of response decisions;
- Execution of a communication policy to the public;
- To effective and timely planning and developing information campaigns able to attract volunteering and prompting safe practices.

Depending on who is going to receive the information and why they need it, two large groups can be distinguished. On the one hand, that person or group of people who require complete situational awareness of an event or situation in order to be able to make decisions based on that knowledge and information. On the other hand, that person or group of people who has to be aware that an event is taking place, without needing to have all the information, in order to execute an action but not a decision.

First responders would be part of the first group, while the general population would be part of the second group.

4.3.2. Practitioner awareness

Having a high-quality situational awareness is deeply important for an effective decision making which, consequently, will lead to concrete actions in these complex and dynamic environments. Originally this term was used in aviation for describing awareness of tactical situations during aerial warfare. It has been adopted to any situations requiring human control.

When, in MCI scenarios, the numerous information systems are individually operational, the interoperability of all these systems is required to obtain the necessary information that provides correct situational awareness and allows making an accurate decision. Data interoperability is assumed to be the path that leads to a Common Operational Picture (COP) and situational awareness.

A COP is a continuously updated overview of an incident compiled throughout an incident's life cycle from data shared between integrated communication, information management, and intelligence and information sharing systems. The goal of a COP is real-time situational awareness across all levels of incident management and across jurisdictions.

A COP is information, tailored in terms of content and detail, geographically represented, that shows the evolution of an event along the progress of the operations merged into a common frame of reference and visualized on a screen, supporting the comprehension by the response organizations of the current view of the situation.

Regarding MCI all involved FRs are aware of the situation while emergency occurs. But on the other side they need to know how many injured people are in the area and their location, what property is at risk, what is the solution of the whole situation, how many sources are needed, etc. It is necessary to get information which can be displayed quickly.

4.3.3. Social awareness

Social awareness can be divided into 3 parts:

1. Pre-incident awareness: involving preparation and prevention tasks
2. Awareness during the incident: public information and population management consisting of early warning of population, informing disabled people, informing people who are only visiting nature and are not familiar with the area, evacuation, etc.)
3. Post-incident awareness: recruitment and management of volunteers to search for missing people, management of evacuated population for their return, rehabilitation of damaged infrastructure.

Social media for emergency management

Social media (SM) can provide near-real-time information for the emergency responders to make effective decisions throughout various stages of the disaster management process. It also facilitates connectedness during the emergency and provides relevant and timely information from both official and non-official sources.

The information available on social media during a crisis, from textual information to information in images and videos, can improve the current information gathering procedures of the EMSs, help them get a better overview of the situation, assess the crisis response effort as well as discover what the people in the affected areas need and how to help them move from danger/warn them.

The utilization of SM for communicating during emergencies was initiated by the public before its utilization by emergency authorities. Social media provides opportunities for engaging citizens in the emergency management by both disseminating information to the public and accessing information from them. The public can assist during emergencies in classifying and sorting the large amount of information flowing. There are different types of information which goes through social media: news, information or updates about the event, personal experiences, personal opinion and interest, jokes, marketing and advertising, humour, concern and/or sadness of the writers towards others, questions about the event.

The identity of users and accuracy of the information they post on social media sites cannot be guaranteed and some of them may be fake news. During emergency events, people are provided with lot of information without being aware of their validity or risk of misinformation. Crowdsourcing of information can be also useful and valuable like the information produced by an expert.

Misinformation can be disseminated during disaster; social media users correct them and also official authorities publish corrections to disinformation using their own social media sites. However, the sheer volume of today's social media presence and the flow of information can make this task quite difficult, which can cause a skewed perspective of the seriousness of the event in place.

In some EU countries VOSTs are operating. VOSTs are highly interesting organisations for study, as their recent emergence reflects some pressing and most debated challenges in disaster

management. VOSTs are a prime example of the effects of digitalisation on emergency management.

4.4. Civil-Military Cooperation

4.4.1. Introduction

The Disaster Management System is a key element of the government and security policy of any country. Internationally, there is no universal model of the management system. Such types of models are in the process of constant transformation and practically cannot be borrowed and copied. In recent years, in many countries, the need to create an effective system for responding to disasters, accidents and catastrophes, through which the functions of the state to guarantee the life and health of the population and the protection of the country's spiritual and material values, are implemented. To solve this problem, a number of legislative and organizational changes were made, different approaches and policies were presented.

The systems of government in each country are a function of the political systems and constitutional order that are unique to each country, and this is where civil-military cooperation comes into play. It is a historical necessity and a necessary constant for the successful realization of the goals of providing humanitarian aid, eliminating the consequences, normalizing public life and restoring statehood. In order to be implemented, it is necessary to use an appropriate conceptual framework that considers Civil-Military Cooperation (CIMIC) not only from the position of the armed forces, but also from that of all other actors.

Nowadays, it is increasingly necessary to use the unique capabilities of the armed forces in the event of catastrophic natural disasters - floods, earthquakes, nuclear accidents and pollution, forest fires, pandemics, etc.

In these cases, the armed forces can provide unique assistance to civilian institutions, such as the provision of military medical facilities and infrastructure, the deployment of field hospitals, the use of military transport to evacuate the wounded and sick; the use of military medical equipment and equipment in the affected area, air monitoring and assessing the extent of damage; ensuring public order and security of infrastructure and property in the disaster area, and others.

For this reason, modern science explores new approaches, mechanisms and possibilities to be implemented within the framework of crisis management that would support effective civilian-military activities between teams of armed forces and civilian structures, building appropriate interface and the necessary joint capabilities for adequate response and overcoming the consequences of such situations.

The present study expects to reveal how civil-military activities and civil-military interaction can be combined within the EU Civil Protection Mechanism and in emergency situations with mass casualties to more effectively use the capabilities of military formations to support civilian institutions in the affected area.

Today is vital to increase a collaboration not only among the search and rescue structures, civil protection teams, emergency and fire services, medical emergency services, but also to harmonize their efforts with non-governmental organizations such as the Red Cross and Red Crescent, various international organizations and those to the UN and the EU, and also the resources, infrastructure, teams, forces and means of the armed forces.

Within the European Union, the growing role of civil-military cooperation was also recognized and the idea of sharing civilian and military capabilities, tools and resources was adopted in the course of humanitarian efforts.

4.4.2. CIMIC in disasters

The main functional areas of action of CIMIC are grouped in five leading areas: public activities, civil infrastructure, humanitarian issues, economy and trade, and cultural issues. Both civil and the military sectors have relevant experience that can be useful to respond to emergencies. The collaboration of the Armed Forces/Military will be requested in accordance with the approved plans of involvement or when the gravity of the situation so requires, according to the availability and priority of military resources, but always within the framework of the respective military commands and specific legislation. On the one hand, the military can contribute to emergency relief through their ability quickly mobilize and send unique assets and experience to distant areas. On the other hand, civil organizations usually have longstanding community relations and are often better equipped to identify the needs of the beneficiaries.

Armed forces, and in particular CIMIC teams, can assist civilian actors. In case of disaster, the condition of the infrastructure can be greatly degraded. Because of this, civil infrastructure components can become completely ineffective (whether due to industrial accident or natural disaster). CIMIC professionals may conduct and provide an assessment to the command level of the state of an area to proactively identify weaknesses and critical gaps or capability gaps in the civilian environment that need to be filled, either temporarily or permanently.

In order to plan the participation of CIMIC specialists, clear and applicable proposals and procedures must be developed for activities within their competence based on compliance with the conditions, the need to assess the factors influencing the civil environment, the population, the authorities, business, international organizations, NGOs, religious organizations and movements. CIMIC specialists can propose (and suggest) models and options for cooperation and coordination between the joint participation of military forces and civil society actors who, by providing the necessary resources, contribute to the execution of the mission in peacetime and in emergency situations.

A very important condition for successful interaction and good coordination is the requirement to have a mutual understanding of the goals, mandates and capabilities of the participants in crisis management.

And also, to have prepared joint response plans, common programs for preparing, training and conducting exercises under uniform scenarios, as well as clear procedures, protocols and standards on the basis of which this interaction is to be carried out.

Finally, it is also important to establish and maintain strong relationships prior to and during the moments of collaboration in order to ensure mutual understanding.

4.5. Civil Protection and Aid Volunteerism

Civil Protection is the public service that protects the citizens from man-made or natural disasters, and participates in different phases of an emergency.

Civil Protection within Europe is organised in different ways at national level according to the internal organisation and regulations of each country. Although there is a large number of bilateral agreements between neighbour countries to cooperate in case of cross-border MCI

based on the past experiences and necessities, a common approach to proceed at European level has not been harmonised.

In 2001 The EU Civil Protection Mechanism (UCPM) was created to improve the coordination of the interventions of the European Civil Protection services in emergencies/disasters in the Member States. The main activities are to facilitate access to material resources and means of transport available in the member and complementary states, give specific trainings and promote simulated exercises to improve preparedness of the Member States.

Civil protection is facing additional challenges resulting from social and demographic changes. First responders are increasingly confronted with situations that require foreign language skills and intercultural competencies, requiring multicultural teams to act jointly or in a complementary manner in relation to these requirements in cross-border MCI.

In an international cross-sectorial emergency, coordination of activities will require a more complex participatory process and hierarchical decision-making systems than in a typical national disaster management.

Assistance during such emergencies requires the availability of staff and resources at very short notice. When situations affect entire regions, cross-border assistance from neighbours is even more necessary, so it is essential to have appropriately trained and motivated volunteers who can help as needed.

It is necessary to develop a framework for profiling of the Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) and volunteers' organisations, as well as the other institutions involved in the Disaster Risk Management (DRM), and promote the availability of a centralized mechanism for registration and activation of voluntary institutions in the form of a rapid response in the event of a disaster.

Developing an ontology of Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) involving volunteers, local multipliers, and policymakers in the reaction phase with proposed measures for involvement of local actors will allow a better response with more coordinated action.

Although civil protection is a national competence, increasing risks do not follow any borders and there is a need to better prepare for cross-border risks, cross-border response and multi-hazards. There is a need to provide a comprehensive compendium of competences/capacities and skills required by each actor to establish the minimum requirements in terms of service resources and preparation of the first responders and volunteers.

The European Commission upgraded the EU Civil Protection Mechanism and created rescEU to reinforce and strengthen components of the EU's disaster risk management. It aims to both protect citizens from disasters and manage emerging risks.

RescEU establishes a new European reserve of resources (the 'rescEU reserve') which includes a fleet of firefighting planes and helicopters, medical evacuation planes, as well as a stockpile of medical items and field hospitals that can respond to health emergencies.

The EU is also developing a reserve to respond to chemical, biological, radiological, and nuclear incidents.

When the scale of an emergency overwhelms the possibilities of a country to respond on its own, it can request assistance via the EU Civil Protection Mechanism.

Once activated, the EU channels through the Emergency Response Coordination Centre the offers of assistance made available by its Member States and Participating States.

5. Identification of gaps

5.1. Resource federation and trusted information sharing

5.1.1. Data federation between organisations

G6.1-1: Non-technological initialization of an emergency.

One of the main gaps in this category is based on the limited capabilities that first responders have in terms of cross-border emergency data federation. Currently, and based on professional experience, when a cross-border situation arises, agencies responsible between countries communicate via telephone to start the actuation.

G6.1-2: Cross-border data exchange in person.

Once the situation has been communicated, then the different resources are placed in the incident area, and, thus they perform communication in place, not using technological solutions for data sharing with foreign agencies.

G6.1-3: Lack of data federation.

There is a lack of data federation between countries in terms of the use of technological solutions. Thus, data is not transmitted automatically or in real time with the affected members of an emergency. This is crucial, as intervening entities need to communicate data in a rudimentary way, either in person or by telephone.

G6.1-4: Legal barriers between countries regarding resource federation.

Gaps existing in legal aspects must also be considered. Particularly, there are legal barriers between countries regarding resource federation. The different EU countries present different regulations regarding data sharing between member countries and complicates the implantation of resource federation strategies.

G6.1-5: Dynamic management of data federation.

Additionally, this gap expresses a necessity for technological data federation approaches in a dynamic way. Particularly, emergency scenarios do not implement strategies for dynamic data federation in a unified way at EU level, which difficult the implantation of these kinds of technologies.

G6.1-16: Federation incompatibilities.

In addition to the previous limitations, there are also gaps in current data federation technologies that could difficult the implantation of these strategies in emergency scenarios. First, there is a coexistence of multiple data federation techniques that present incompatibilities, as it is the case of OAuth 2.0 and OAuth 1.0 (see G6.1-16).

G6.1-17: OAuth2 – Complex management.

Focusing particularly on OAuth 2.0, it presents a complex management, since the use of this protocol is difficulties when a substantial number of institutions intervene in the federation.

G6.1-18: OAuth2 – Centralised authorisation server.

This technology also presents a limitation concerning the authorisation server, as it is centralised and could become a single point of failure in case of attacks against the federation infrastructure.

G6.1-19: Shibboleth – Lack of generalised logout capabilities.

Another promising initiative, Shibboleth, also present limitations that could difficult the implantation of global resource federation initiatives at EU level. First, it lacks generalised logout capabilities in its standard. That is to say, Shibboleth cannot perform a logout over all services federated at the same time.

G6.1-20: Shibboleth – High implementation complexity.

Moreover, Shibboleth is highly complex, whose configuration of proxy servers difficult the implantation of a Shibboleth infrastructure.

5.1.2. Mechanism to provide data confidentiality**G6.1-21: Quantum Menace.**

The Quantum threat would be able to vulnerate current cryptosystems and that should be taken into account while handling sensitive data, as it is the objective of harvest attacks whose objective is to collect data that will be deciphered later.

G6.1-22: Computational cost and G6.1-8: Asymmetric cryptography is slow.

The main problem regarding the mechanisms to provide data confidentiality relies in their computational capabilities. This includes the capabilities required to encrypt the data, to decrypt the data and the capabilities necessary to venerate a certain cryptosystem. In relation to this, this gap identifies the need to use light cryptographic mechanisms that can be used during the emergency actuations, which is related to the G6.1-8, as the asymmetric cryptography tend to be slower than symmetric cryptography.

G6.1-23: Key distribution.

In relation to the previous G6.1-21, this gap addresses the problematic of a deficient key distribution, as it would weaken the whole cryptosystem due to the fact that a compromised key distribution leads to a compromised cryptosystem.

5.1.3. Mechanism to provide resource integrity

Resources integrity in a federated system addresses mostly about data and information resources. The data integrity between solution and systems that are independent and which to exchange information requires a common understanding of the data exchanged, its formats, protocols, topology, structures, and common language.

G6.1-24: Distributed technologies.

As the use of distributed technologies is limited by the use of devices which are able to support this kind of technologies, this gap addresses the problematic of using distributed technologies such as blockchain during the emergency actuations.

G6.1-25: PKI availability and G6.1-7: Asymmetric cryptography requires a complex infrastructure.

A crucial point of the key distribution is addressed in the gap G6.1-25, as the PKI should be available during the actuations in order to actually distribute the keys. This gap is related to the gap G6.1-7, as the PKI required for asymmetric cryptography is complex.

G6.1-6: Used of pre-shared keys in symmetric cryptography.

Overall, the need of a secure key storage and handling, as they allow the access to the communication flow. This means that the entities sharing data must use a common reference. However, each entity holds their own solutions, and have a history developed through centuries, regarding procedures and data organization, classification, etc.

G6.1-9: Data redundancy requires a considerable increase in disk space.

Moreover, data redundancy presents several limitations that need to be considered. First, data redundancy requires a considerable increase in disk space compared to not using these techniques. For example, techniques such as RAID induce an increase in disk space necessary to offer data redundancy.

G6.1-10: Data redundancy need to keep data up to date.

Additionally, these redundant data must be kept up to date, which increases the complexity of the implementation.

G6.1-11: Inconsistencies in data redundancy.

The application of data redundancy techniques may introduce inconsistencies, as the different nodes storing data may end up having different contents or versions, and thus generate important issues.

G6.1-26: Common data language

To enable the good communication by Joint forces and a multiple entities and cross border environment, involving different languages, a common reference language helps and facilitates the comprehension and supports a clearer communication. By establishing the reference language, it is up to each entity to either use that reference language or to translate to its own language.

G6.1-27: Common data Taxonomy

Following and complementing the previous gap, also a coherent and common taxonomy reference enables good communication and helps automate several of the processes.

G6.1-28: Tampered data

To support the trustworthiness of the information exchange, it is of the utmost relevancy that the data is secured but also the potentially tampered data to be clearly identified and detected, while keeping the system versatile. Therefore, the ability to store the messages metadata in a Blockchain structure allows the identification of tampered data and supports data auditing processes.

G6.1-29: Dynamic reference schema

For a question of versatility, the core communication elements: language, taxonomies and data models are very diversified, depending on the events, entities and countries involved. Therefore, to support the multiple combination between such core communication structures, the data/messages/protocols/etc, in a multi country forces, different data schemas can be establishing. By supporting multiple schemas and dynamic usage of those schemas, enables an easy translation and conversion of the data core communication elements.

G6.1-30: COP marking data source

An important operational ability in a federated systems are the understanding of the data displayed by the COP (Common Operational Picture), where each system has its own COP. By displaying simultaneously its own data as well as external data (shared), it may be relevant for the decision-maker to know the nature of the source of the data that support the decision. Therefore, the COP could provide such information, by distinguish the own data and external data.

G6.1-31: Backup data

The system should be resilient to potential hazardous data loss events by providing data backup capability either at SIGRUN / federation level, as well as local backup capability for the cases where connectivity to the networks backup servers is lost.

5.1.4. Mechanism to provide availability of the collaboration

G6.1-12: Emergency entities do not use dynamic network management techniques

Current network solutions used in emergency scenarios do not have dynamic behaviors, not being able to be reconfigured in real time to adapt to traffic demands, congestion or even cyberattacks. Based on that, the disasters that are common in emergency situations could disrupt communication due to limitations in existing emergency networks.

G6.1-13: On-demand security capabilities

Current communication networks in emergency domains do not offer on-demand security capabilities, enable the deployment of security functions based on the status of the network or the detection of security threats. Thus, these networks behave in a static way, analysing the traffic transmitted in the network and reacting to it. Based on that, the use of software defined network and network virtualisation functions could help providing dynamic security capabilities to emergency communication networks.

When it comes to the success of any form of activity, collaboration is one of the most important factors. Without effective collaboration, no project will succeed, thus ensuring that it is implemented smoothly should be a major focus.

One of the most crucial skills for success is the capacity for teamwork. Different actors engage in cooperation when they work together to achieve a common goal, either individually or as a team. This concept expands in a project setting to include partners and team members working on certain tasks that call for frequent communication and teamwork. An effective workflow requires efficient collaboration, which involves seamless, open communication between all parties involved, especially when taking on large tasks. It makes operations more efficient and

increases the likelihood of success and also encourages couples to have positive working connections.

Modern Project execution combines traditional techniques with cutting-edge, high-tech communication tools to build frameworks that work for every team member. Collaborators can locate all of their necessary tools and resources on one platform within a collaborative framework. Through that framework, they might also coordinate and communicate with one another, which would enable them to finish their work much more swiftly.

However, the reliance on digital tools, however, may also bring certain difficulties. To collaborate and access each other's files and documents, collaborators typically need to switch between various apps and/or platforms. This can gobble up time that might have been better spent moving the task along. Specifically for emergency scenarios, where time is of the essence, every second counts, thus, wasting time is an undoubtedly an unaffordable luxury. In addition, various systems may be required to interconnect and interact. In multi-victim incidents such interactions should work seamlessly in order to provide the best possible quality of service.

Of course, it's not always simple to achieve constant and seamless collaboration. Collaboration can occasionally suffer from a lack of open communication among team members and equipment or from the absence of a common framework for everyone to send and receive crucial information.

The lack of concrete frameworks that will facilitate smooth operations in information sharing, in various forms, poses a severe challenge for disaster management scenarios, especially when it comes to bringing together collaborators from different countries, where processes, equipment and protocols may substantially vary.

For disaster management, efficient collaboration, capacity for teamwork, properly established frameworks, effective workflows, etc., all share a common denominator: the constant availability of collaboration which translates into systems designed to provide high uptimes and QoS. Mechanisms that can cover all relevant needs in a holistic way are of utmost importance and need to be specifically designed for the use-cases that will be called to serve.

G6.1-34 Trusted minimum requirements

The use of partially implemented frameworks that provide security for specific uses, and consequently create a feeling of low security in the context of international or cross-border operations, since the current frameworks are not focused on this area of international collaboration.

5.1.5. Frameworks offering data federation

G6.1-14: Lack of standardised frameworks for data federation.

There are a lot and different frameworks offering data federation. These frameworks are developed by different organisations but none is selected as a standard that should be used by every participant in an emergency. Not even within the European Union.

G6.1-15: Existing frameworks are specific

Current information sharing frameworks were created with a specific porpoise. Then, later the frameworks extend the data to provide the functionalities required to manage the emergency.

But the capabilities required by each of the emergency stakeholders are not fully covered based in the specific porpoise.

G6.1-33: Lack of interoperability between frameworks offering data federation

There is no interoperability between the frameworks offering data federation. First of all, it is difficult to achieve engagement of the organization to provide information. Any organization want to review that their information is managed correctly. A framework manages multi-sources information so it is even more difficult due to interoperability between frameworks.

G6.1-35 Unhelpful information provided by the frameworks

Limited use of the framework due to conflicts of responsibilities or functions, developing functions in a limited way. The contribution of the information is partial, focused on responding to specific cases of frequent use.

Identification of gaps			
Resource federation and trusted information sharing			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G6.1-1	Non-technological initialisation of an emergency.	Professional experience	Communication between EU countries in cross-border incidents do not employ technological solutions for data exchange between countries. They typically communicate via phone.
G6.1-2	Cross-border data exchange in person.	Professional experience	Once the emergency is communicated, effectives from the affected countries move to the incident area and exchange information from the intervening agencies in person, without using technological solutions between countries.
G6.1-3	Lack of data federation between countries	Professional experience	EU countries do not implement data federation techniques to share information automatically and in real time with affected members of an emergency.
G6.1-4	Legal barriers between countries regarding resource federation	Literature	EU countries have different regulations in terms of data sharing between member countries and difficult the implantation of resource federation strategies.
G6.1-5	Dynamic management of data federation	Professional experience	There is a lack of dynamic data federation strategies in emergency scenarios.
G6.1-6	Use of pre-shared keys in symmetric cryptography	Professional experience	Symmetric cryptography uses pre-shared keys that, if stolen, could allow attackers to get access to the entire communication flow.
G6.1-7	Asymmetric cryptography requires a complex infrastructure	Literature	Asymmetric cryptography requires a complex hierarchy of certification authorities and trust relationships.

Identification of gaps			
Resource federation and trusted information sharing			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G6.1-8	Asymmetric cryptography is slow	Literature	Asymmetric cryptography operations are slower than those performed by symmetric cryptography.
G6.1-9	Data redundancy requires a considerable increase in disk space	Professional experience	The use of data redundancy techniques, such as RAID, substantially increase the disk space required to store the information.
G6.1-10	Data redundancy need to keep data up to date	Professional experience	Data coherence between data storage nodes increases the complexity to keep data up to date
G6.1-11	Inconsistencies in data redundancy	Professional experience	Distributed data in different nodes augments the likelihood of having inconsistent data.
G6.1-12	Emergency entities do not use dynamic network management techniques	Professional experience, Survey	Emergency environments use static networks for providing services, not considering dynamic network approaches such as SDN.
G6.1-13	On-demand security capabilities	Professional experience.	Emergency organisations do not implement capabilities to offer security actuations on demand.
G6.1-14	Lack of standardised frameworks for data federation	Professional experience and literature	Although there are several frameworks available for data federation, none is widely used by emergency organisations at EU level.
G6.1-15	Existing frameworks are specific	Professional experience and literature	Current frameworks available are not general enough to be used in multidisciplinary emergency scenarios.
G6.1-16	Federation incompatibilities	Professional experience	The coexistence of multiple data federation techniques might present incompatibilities, such as OAuth 2.0 and its incompatibility with OAuth 1.0.
G6.1-17	OAuth2 - Complex management	Literature	The management of OAuth2 becomes complex when a substantial number of institutions intervene.
G6.1-18	OAuth2 - Centralised authorisation server	Professional experience	The authorisation server could be a single point of failure in case of attacks.
G6.1-19	Shibboleth - Lack of generalised logout capabilities	Literature	Shibboleth is not able to perform a logout action over all services federated at the same time.
G6.1-20	Shibboleth - High implementation complexity	Literature	The configuration of proxy servers is a complex task that difficult the implantation of a Shibboleth infrastructure.

Identification of gaps			
Resource federation and trusted information sharing			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G6.1-21	Quantum Menace	Literature	The threat that of the quantum computing against the current cryptosystems and the harvest-now-decrypt-later attacks.
G6.1-22	Computational cost	Literature	The computational cost required during cryptographic processes during emergency actuations might pose as an obstacle.
G6.1-23	Key distribution	Literature	An inappropriate or insecure key distribution can venerate the whole cryptosystem.
G6.1-24	Distributed technologies	Literature	Distributed integrity mechanisms, such as Blockchain, might not be suitable for all the devices involved.
G6.1-25	PKI availability	Literature	The unavailability of PKI would disable the use of asymmetric schemes.
G6.1-26	Common data language	Professional experience	Define a common reference language for different entities and countries to support data integrity.
G6.1-27	Common data taxonomy	Professional experience	Define a common reference taxonomy for different entities and countries to classify data.
G6.1-28	Tampered data	Professional experience and literature	Use of Blockchain to detect tampered data and data auditing.
G6.1-29	Dynamic reference schema	Professional experience	Schema database to support different data integrity models.
G6.1-30	COP marking data source	Professional experience and Literature	COP marks the data displayed according to the data source (own or external).
G6.1-31	Backup data	Professional experience	Backup and restore data to mitigate data loss.
G6.1-32	Country specific requirements on exchange of personal / sensitive data	Professional experience, country specific GDRP law requirements	No possibility to legally exchange personal / sensitive data except via recognised international organisations. Access to personal / sensitive data should be arranged only via local GDRP law requirements.
G6.1-33	Lack of interoperability between frameworks offering data federation	Professional experience and literature	The different frameworks do not offer interoperability between them. This makes it difficult to share information between organisations.
G6.1-34	Trusted minimum requirements	Professional experience and literature	Lack of collaboration on data sharing due to lack of trusted minimum requirements

Identification of gaps			
Resource federation and trusted information sharing			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G6.1-35	Unhelpful information provided by the frameworks	Professional experience and literature	Lack of collaboration in data exchange due to unhelpful information provided by the frameworks

Table 2 – Gaps from Task 6.1 Resource federation and trusted information sharing

5.2. Education and training for first aid responses

G6.2-1: European curricula for Basic First Aid.

E&T of first aid responders varies within European countries, which makes cross-border cooperation difficult. There is no common curriculum for Basic First Aid in emergency medicine to ensure a comparable knowledge base to provide equivalent services between countries. At a national level, there is a lack of mandatory courses to further increase healthcare professionals' skillsets; during the training of a nurse, in Portugal, only the Basic Life Support course is mandatory, and it is the responsibility of the nurse to further acquire knowledge through Advanced Life Support, who only does it if he/she so wishes to or has the resources.

G6.2-2: Lack of standard for cross-border recognition of first aid courses.

There are different first aid certificates for a minimum knowledge base in first aid at the National/European level, but these are issued by non-profit organisations such as the International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies (IFRC) or Samaritan International 2 and are not universally valid due to the lack of standard for cross-border recognition of first aid courses in the EU. Until there is an international protocol that defines these competencies, the minimum requirements should be those that are used nowadays, and those that are legally required by each country.

G6.2-3: The specialty of emergency medicine.

The specialty of emergency medicine is not recognised in all EU countries. It would be appropriate for the specialty to be recognised at European level in order to comply with the EU Doctors Directive and to ensure the free exchange of doctors between EU countries. There is a Need to standardise the E&T of FARs within the European MS, to create a common curriculum for Basic First Aid in emergency medicine.

G6.2-4: Lack of homogeneity in the provision of health resources for emergency and urgent care.

Lack of homogeneity in the provision of health resources for emergency care. In most European countries, emergency care teams consist of a doctor, a nurse and an ambulance driver. In most countries, non-urgent care teams consist of one or two nurses, emergency medical technicians or assistants accompanied by an ambulance driver. Doctors are not part of the non-emergency ambulance staff.

There are specific rules for ambulances in each country. What all ambulance personnel do receive is specific training.

G6.2-5: Variable training of paramedics in European countries.

In the European countries there is a growing need for highly trained paramedics. Paramedic training varies in European countries. Paramedics do not have comparable knowledge bases and are not be able to provide equivalent services between countries

In some countries a bachelor's degree is required, while in others the courses are shorter and of a lower academic level. Cross-border ICM cooperation requires paramedics to have comparable knowledge bases and to be able to provide equivalent services between countries.

G6.2-6: Lack of homogeneity in the response to multi-victim incidents.

Lack of uniformity in the response to multi-victim incidents. Not all EU countries have a national standard operating procedure for the management of mass casualty incidents or disasters. In some cases, procedures exist at regional level but there is no standardisation at national level. This makes coordination and interoperability difficult in cross-border disasters where coordination is established at that administrative level.

G6.2-7: Ownership of emergency services.

Emergency services have different ownership in EU countries. In some cases, they are privately owned, in others, they are publicly owned... This different dependency makes standardisation difficult in areas such as staff training, multi-agency education, research and development. This lack of standardisation is a hindrance to cross-sectoral and cross-border cooperation.

G6.2-8: Lack of cooperation and mutual assistance between first aid providers.

Lack of cooperation and mutual assistance between first aid providers. Each institution, organisation and team have the necessary training, skills and knowledge to deal with the emergency, but there are deficiencies in terms of communication and coordination between institutions. Considering that multiple mass casualty and disaster incident management involves different action groups, each of which integrates different emergency services, such coordination should be appropriate in order to ensure an efficient response to the emergency.

G6.2-9: No standardised reporting after MCI and debriefing/G6.2-12: No centralised "lessons learned database" for FAR at European level.

Lessons learned from simulations or real emergencies are valuable information for collective learning among countries or other stakeholders to strengthen preparedness and global response to emergencies. The debriefing process to capture these lessons learned does not always occur, it is not standardised and its dissemination is very limited.

A common approach in the post-disaster social and psychosocial support of victims, as well as first responders absent.

G.6.2-10: Lack of common methodology for the organisation of training exercises for first responders.

The organisation of exercises is one of the most important activities for the training of first responders. Through these exercises first responders' operational capacities are improved, thus facilitating response in real-life emergencies and operations. Exercises are the means to assess and test the performance of organisations against specific plans, protocols, agreements, policies

and operational procedures (USDHS, 2020). Through exercises also the cross-sector and cross-border cooperation aspect is examined, therefore highlighting emerging interoperability gaps.

Interoperability can be examined under two different angles:

- Technical interoperability, under the framework of which the communication between different technological systems, or the interconnection between several different subsystems of the same system is assessed.
- Procedural interoperability, which takes into consideration and examines the level of cooperation and coordination between different first responders' organisations or between different units of the same organisation.

Training exercises could be a means for enhancing interoperability, especially in terms of the procedural strand. A common approach for the organisation of training exercises is a serious gap in disaster management, according to Sakkas et al. (2020). Although this issue has been addressed by the standardisation domain, it largely remains an aspect, on which current and future research and standardisation activities should focus. At present, there are standards, which topic is related to the organisation of first responders' training, in general, and of exercises, particularly, e.g., ISO 22398:2013 "Security and Resilience – Emergency Management – Guidelines for exercises", ASTM F2751-16 "Standard Guide for Training of a Land Search and Rescue Team Member". Additionally, to this direction, pre-standardisation activities (development of CWAs (CEN Workshop Agreements)), inside the European Committee for Standardization (CEN) are currently taking place, which is related to the development and outline of evaluation processes for crisis management exercises.

However, according to Tsaloukidis et al. (2022), first responders seem to be unaware of the existence of standards or they are reluctant to integrate and implement them in their organisations, whereas, on the other hand, they do prefer the implementation of widely adopted guidelines. In this research, which was conducted in the context of the H2020 FIRE-IN project, a survey was developed, addressing two main groups of stakeholders: a) technological providers and b) first responders. From the survey it was derived that, although technology and standardisation enhance the capacity of first responders and enable and facilitate more effective operations, a large proportion of the participants does not make use of formal standards, i.e., standards developed by official national, EU and international standardisation bodies, or they are not aware of whether these standards are implemented inside the operational protocols of their organisations. On the other hand, organisations, either civilian or military, with a significant outreach in the disaster and crisis management community e.g., INSARAG, IFRC, NATO, have developed best practices and guidelines. Specifically, regarding the training of personnel and the organisation of exercises, different agencies have developed different approaches. Examples of such approaches could be the Exercise and Evaluation Program (HSEEP) from the United States Department of Homeland Security (USDHS, 2020) or the Exercise Guidance manual from the Swedish Civil Contingencies Agency (MSB, 2017). Such approaches might be adopted by several organisations, thus leading to different methodologies in conducting training exercises.

Nevertheless, standardisation is the most efficient way for a uniform approach, especially when discussion comes to cross-border interoperability. The transformation of widely adopted guidelines and procedures into standards would solve cross-border interoperability issues and lead to the adoption of common methodologies in general, and to common ways for the organisation of training exercises for first responders in particular. Since cross-border interoperability is one of the core focal points of the Valkyries project, a cohesive plan for the

organisation of exercises should be considered as a basic challenge to be addressed. More effort should be put and focus on joint exercises for first responders firstly at national level and cross-sectorial level and also stress the attention for cross-border cooperation and exercises which should result to interoperability. Good relationship between EU countries and lessons learnt play a significant role to reach this goal.

G6.2-11: Lack of first responders' training in new technological solutions.

Technology evolves rapidly and, as a result of this evolution, state of the art technological innovations related to disaster management are constantly being developed. These innovations are meant to enhance first responders' capabilities and provide new tools to fight off the consequences of disasters. But are first responders ready to use these technologies? Are they sufficiently trained to operate cutting edge software, hardware or equipment?

Nowadays, many different types of technologies are being produced. Such technologies could be for instance command and control systems, GIS and geolocation systems, sensors for early detection of fire, smoke, dangerous CBRN agents, weather forecasting systems, equipment for first responders (smart textiles, exoskeletons for firefighters), AR/VR/XR software for training simulations, propagation models, big data analysis systems, Artificial Intelligence and technologies for robust communications.

According to Tsaloukidis et.al. (2022) and the survey conducted in the framework of their research, first responders consider technology as a very efficient way for increasing their capacities in first response operations. However, many end users do not consider themselves as adequately trained to the operation of state-of-the-art technologies. Taking into account their point of view, new technologies should become easier to use. First responders, during operations, should operate user friendly and straightforward systems, thus limiting response times and enhancing their capacity. Furthermore, scientific tools and instruments may require more scientific competence than the majority of the first responders has. A solution could be the inclusion of initial and of recurring training to new technologies within the training protocols of first responders' organisations. Nevertheless, according to the survey, this is not the case for a significant percentage of first responders. Thus, it is evident that this gap i.e., the lack of training in novel solutions, exists, not only at a theoretical but also at a practical level.

Apart from the first responders' training, other reasons also exist. A reluctance in the use of state-of-the-art technologies is apparent. According to Tsaloukidis et al. (2022) high procurement costs and procedures could be an answer. Moreover, first responders seem hesitant and conservative, staying attached to the same technological providers and older technologies, with which they are familiar and comfortable to use. Another reason could be the lack of awareness of new technologies. Regardless of the reason, the fact remains that first responders remain, to a significant degree, either inadequately trained or agnostic to novel solutions, a gap that should be greatly considered in the context not only of the Valkyries project but of disaster management in general.

G6.2-12: Knowledge, skills and competency spread between various groups of healthcare professionals who are tasked to participate in the management of MCI / G6.2-13: Didactical level of trainings.

It is necessary to define the desired competencies for training for MCI and disasters. Without them it is difficult to determine the content and methodology of the proposed training. Well

formulated competences constitute the basis for building effective and targeted training. The teaching and training of competencies is based on integrated medical education, and the number of competency profiles for health care professionals may vary depending on the profession being trained.

G6.2-14: Lack of rescuers with full medical education.

Situation with EMS and globally with health care professionals is not favourable and there is a shortage of health care professionals. It is probable that some positions within health care providers are represented by let's say with professionals with very little medical education.

G6.2-15: Lack of common organizational structure and rules regarding collaboration between first aid responders / G6.2-16: Lack of uniform national standards for FARs / G6.2-17: Lack of capabilities for medical evacuating (MEDEVAC) by air.

Planning as a process - and accompanying plans as part of prevention in Bulgaria is carried out at the national level. At present, protection against disasters is organized on the basis of the following regulatory documents: Disaster Protection Law, National Disaster Risk Reduction Strategy 2018 – 2030. But several problems could be indicated – there is no analysis of threats vulnerabilities and the risk of disasters occurring on the territory of the country. The normative documents present generalized information of the disasters which are specific for the country and also the bodies that are engaged with management. The plans that are prepared at the regional level do not contain measures that must be taken as prevention in order to prevent occurrence of natural disasters or their degree of intensity, but are aimed at the response itself after the disaster has occurred. All of this causes lack of common organizational structure and rules regarding collaboration between first aid responders and uniform national standards for FARs.

The absence of threat and risk analysis deprives the entire system of reliability and expediency in performing the tasks- reducing the probability of occurrence and limiting the size of the negative effects of disasters. Planning as a process must be contained in all elements of the protection actions at disasters, which will ensure stability in the management of the crisis itself. The better the risks and threats are analysed and assessed, the protection resources are planned and the obligations of those involved in the protection process are defined and ensured in the execution of the tasks, the less would be the losses to the state and society as well the possibility of long-term planning and investment in the sites and territories vulnerable to natural disasters.

G6.2-18: Lack of a common, national picture of vehicles/ambulances.

In Greece, there is no available common information system that provides the available vehicle resources. Only 2 different systems are available in different regions, which works separately for each region. In the rest Greek territory, the ambulance service stations are used local systems for coordination of the fleet.

In Greece, the provision of emergency pre-hospital care is provided free of charge through the National Center for Emergency Care (EKAV – Ethniko Kentro Amesis Voitheias). EKAV is based in Athens and is divided into 12 regional stations where it serves cases of emergency medical care and transport to the hospital.

The central service of EKAV in Athens uses the "EKAV Vehicle Routing, Monitoring and Coordination System" which enables the coordination centre to have a complete image of the available vehicles in the field operating in real-time. Furthermore, it offers the ability to assign a vehicle to an incident and track the route.

This system, however, is only available for the central service of EKAV in Athens (as stated on the official website of EKAV). Furthermore, for the Thessaloniki Branch of EKAV there is a separate telecommunications and management system developed by the Region of Central Macedonia. Lastly, all other dispatch centers of the ambulance service in Greece use local systems to control and monitor their fleet.

Thus, it is easy to understand that there is no available common operational picture of the ambulance fleet in the territory and in addition, the assignment of a vehicle at the national level by a Central Coordination Center is limited.

G6.2-19: Differences in the level of E&T (Medical doctors, nurses/equivalent, paramedics, etc.).

At the pre-hospital level, there are 3 main categories of professionals. The medical doctor, the physician and the paramedic. However, at the European level, there is no standardization of procedures and there are two main concepts: Franco-German and Anglo-American. There are many differences between these two concepts. Different countries around the EU follow different models according to their needs, resources, geographical factors etc.

Different models require different types of expert personnel in the field. As a result, there is no shared level of knowledge, even worse in a cross-border mass casualty event where collaboration between two (or more) countries is needed. This gap can be easily combined with the following G6.2-18 with the types of FARs in Greece.

Thus, more research is needed to determine whether it affects mortality rates as well.

G6.2-20: Lack of national standards and criteria for certification of FARs in Greece.

According to the available staffing positions at EKAV (the National Center for Immediate Assistance, which is the ambulance service in Greece), the training of the personnel is divided into two groups, the Paramedics and Doctors.

Paramedics are required to attend a two-year study program from Vocation training Institutes (Public or Private) according to the training program established by the General Secretariat for Lifelong Learning (a special department of the Ministry of Education and Religious Affairs). Doctors are required to have graduated from a medical school (in Greece and/or abroad) and may attend a pre-hospital emergency care program.

The gap that is found, however, is not in the group of doctors but in the group of Paramedics. According to the courses they attend, they receive the necessary knowledge and experience required according to international protocols for their involvement in respective incidents. But what is missing from their educational circle is their international certification by international organizations. For example, they are not certified through the PHTLS (Pre-Hospital Trauma Life Support) or TFR (trauma First Responder) program but they have gone through the corresponding training.

G6.2-21: Absence of unified lessons learned data base created for collection and dissemination of experiences of FARs at the EU level.

Despite the efforts of the UCPM Lessons Learnt Programme, there is no established LL data base to create opportunities for identification and sharing of lessons and good practices from UCPM deployments and horizontal, cross-cutting activities to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of the UCPM as a whole. Lessons from UCPM deployments can provide guidance as to what lessons could be implemented in the future to continually improve the UCPM. A good example in this regard is the main UCPM Lessons Learnt Programme document which is the annual report, a tool for UCPM member and participating states and the Commission to enhance the implementation of lessons and good practices. The absence of unified LL data base makes difficult collaboration among first responders.

G6.2-22: Insufficient joint multinational training for first responders.

Currently, different EU MS provide variety of training courses for First Responders that are though separately for medical first responders, firefighters, military personnel, civil protection, and other institutions responsible for reacting in case of a large-scale crisis situation that creates difficulties in communication and cooperation among first responders. Therefore, it is very important to develop, test and standardise an advanced education and training kit focused on cross-border MCI for first responders at the European level and corresponding to national guidelines.

Identification of gaps			
Education and training for first aid responses			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G6.2-1	European curricula for Basic First Aid	Literature	Cross-border co-operation in MCI requires comparable knowledge bases to provide equivalent services between countries.
G6.2-2	Lack of standard for cross-border recognition of first aid courses	Literature	It is not a universally valid European First Aid Certificate that guarantees a minimum knowledge base in first aid at within Europe.
G6.2-3	The specialty of emergency medicine	Literature	The specialty of emergency medicine is not recognised in all EU countries. It would be appropriate for the specialty to be recognised at European level in order to comply with the EU Doctors Directive and to ensure the free exchange of doctors between EU countries.
G6.2-4	Lack of homogeneity in the provision of health resources for emergency and urgent care.	Literature	In most European countries, emergency care teams consist of a doctor, nurse and ambulance driver. Doctors are not part of the non-emergency ambulance staff.
G6.2-5	Variable training of paramedics in European countries.	Literature	Cross-border cooperation in MCI requires paramedics to have comparable knowledge bases and be able to provide equivalent services between countries.

Identification of gaps			
Education and training for first aid responses			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G6.2-6	Lack of homogeneity in the response to multi-victim incidents.	Literature	In some countries there is no national standard operating procedure for dealing with multi-victim incidents.
G6.2-7	Ownership of emergency services.	Literature	The different ownership of emergency services (public, private...) hinders multi-agency training and education, as well as research and development. This hampers inter-sectoral cooperation.
G6.2-8	Lack of cooperation and mutual assistance between first aid providers	Literature	Each institution, organisation and team have the necessary skills and has the knowledge of the reaction but does not have the right communication and coordination system to achieve the best possible results.
G6.2-9	No standardised reporting after ICM and debriefing Absence of a common approach in the post-disaster social and psychosocial support of victims as well as first responders	Literature	There is no standardised reporting or debriefing after the management of an ICM, which would allow for a comparison of responses and lessons learned that could improve the response.
G6.2-10	Lack of common methodology for the organisation of training exercises for first responders and no joint trainings for first responders	Literature/ Professional experience	Currently there is not a common way for the organisation of first responders' training exercises. Many first responders' organisations have developed guidelines for the planning, conduct and evaluation of training exercises but no universal approach exists.
G6.2-11	Lack of first responders' training in new technological solutions.	Literature, Survey	New technological innovations emerge, which can greatly facilitate first responders in their operations. However, if first responders are not sufficiently trained to use these technologies beforehand, this may result in reluctance and attachment in older and less effective solutions.
G6.2-12	Knowledge, skills and competency spread between various groups of healthcare	Literature	The pathway to acquiring MCI and disaster management competencies is to obtain appropriate knowledge and skills

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Identification of gaps			
Education and training for first aid responses			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
	professionals who are tasked to participate in the management of MCI		that are reinforced through consistent drills and evaluations
G6.2-13	Didactical level of trainings	Literature	Many trainings or courses aim to deliver a didactical level of knowledge. Participants/professionals participate in educational initiatives without having any knowledge of disaster management principles, i.e., command, control, communication, coordination and collaboration.
G6.2-14	Lack of rescuers with full medical education	Professional experience	Emergency medical care provided to victims by rescuers with very little medical education.
G6.2-15	Lack of common organizational structure and rules regarding collaboration between first aid responders	Literature	More of the documents concerning protocols, standards and etc. are connected with a different level of administrative structures.
G6.2 – 16	Lack of uniform national standards for FARs	Literature	Most of the documents imply common information regarding the organization for first aid process.
G6.2- 17	Lack of capabilities for medical evacuating (MEDEVAC) by air	Literature	There are shortages regarding not having helicopters, system and pilots for medical evacuation by air. This prevents the execution of actions with a specialized helicopter. The military helicopters which are used in emergency situations are not suitable for these purposes.
G.6.2-18	Lack of a common, national picture of vehicles/ambulances	Literature review and professional experience	In Greece, there is no available common information system that provides the available vehicle resources. Only 2 different systems are available in different regions.
G.6.2-19	Differences in the level of E&T (Medical doctors,	Literature review and professional experience	At the EU level there is no standardization of procedures and there are two main concepts: European and Anglo-American.

Identification of gaps			
Education and training for first aid responses			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
	nurses/equivalent, paramedics, etc.)		
G.6.2-20	Lack of national standards and criteria for certification of FARs in Greece	Professional experience	There is a lack of certification in the training of medical first responders.
G.6.2-21	There are no lessons learned data base for collection and dissemination of experiences of FARs	Literature and professional experience	Despite the efforts of the UCPM Lessons Learnt Programme, there is no established LL data base to create opportunities for identification and sharing of lessons and good practices from UCPM deployments and horizontal, cross-cutting activities to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of the UCPM as a whole.
G6.2-22:	Insufficient joint multinational training for first responders.	Literature and professional experience, Survey	There is clear need to develop, test and standardise an advanced education and training kit focused on cross-border MCI for first responders at the European level and according to national guidelines.

Table 3 – Gaps from education and training for first aid responses

5.3. Raising practitioner and social awareness

G6.3-1: Lack of interoperability in communication tools.

Inadequate and incompatible technology with poorly equipped command centre is limiting factors during multi-agency coordination of each MCI. Incompatibility of technology, especially in communication matrix between agencies of first responders, will reduce the overall efficiency response. This is due to the inability of each first responder agency to communicate up to date information to the other agencies involved. Inadequate communication devices inside the same entity can also lead to loss of information, as is the case with limited range of operation between devices and lack of supporting networks.

A lack of definition is detected regarding the interfaces between different applications and tools, which involves the definition of the minimum data set to be transmitted (currently under development in the project), the definition of a unified data format or a gateway that allows the translation of the data from a source format to a destination format, the degree of the data processing that each tool requires (that is, completely processed data, partially processed data or raw data).

G6.3-2: Hoaxes.

Using the information published by people who are close to the emergency area can provide very relevant information for the first responders, such as, a first estimate of the magnitude of the damage, the location and condition of the victims, affected areas and infrastructure, presence of events derived from the main disaster (fires, leaks of toxic substances, etc.). This type of information received from early times and updated in near real time is the first step in establishing early situational awareness for first responders and, in turn, alerts the population that an MCI has taken place.

However, the information shared and disseminated on social media does not have a seal of validity and veracity such as that provided by official bodies. This poses a risk since the data, images and videos posted and, on occasions, virilised, may contain inaccurate or even manipulated and false information. Examples of the enormous spread of fake news have recently been observed in the conflict between Russia and Ukraine, where images of the wounded and deceased corresponding to other conflicts in other countries or in the past have been disseminated on SM.

In this context, the difficulty lies in the detection and filtering of unnecessary or malicious information so that the extracted data can serve to increase the situational awareness of the first responders and the awareness of the population.

G6.3-3 Lack of understanding between agencies.

It is the responsibility of each representative to record the information as required, it is a government problem in managing MCI. Lack of information management and lack of an appropriate common operational picture is information management limiting factors. This gap includes the communication of inaccurate or incomplete information between first responders' agencies, the difference in terms used in information sharing, inability to understand other first agencies information, and poor information management. Paton and Flin (1999) also stated that good communication is essential in ensuring appropriate information is available and delivered promptly.

G6.3-4 Alternative communication system.

During an MCI, especially a natural disaster such as earthquake or explosion events, the probability that communications infrastructures near the disaster will be damaged is high. This implies a reduction in coverage or, in extreme cases, the complete loss of the signal that impacts two areas. On the one hand, in the population, which will have difficulties to communicate with the emergency services, with their relatives, to post information on social networks (as mentioned in G6.3-2) and to receive notifications from the responsible body about the evacuation plan and the necessary instructions for the population, thus hindering the task of generating social awareness. On the other hand, it will affect the emergency teams themselves where the importance of establishing and maintaining a deployable communications capability during MCI stands out. This includes having multiple modes of communication as well as an alternative communication system.

G6.3-5 Lack of public awareness.

The low level of public awareness of the dangers, possible consequences and readiness for adequate response in early warning and disaster disclosure is an essential problem which requires the development and implementation of a Strategy for public awareness for the relevant territorial districts.

G6.3-6 Communication language.

Cross-border disasters that affect two or more countries pose a challenge when establishing contact with the population and between the first responders of the affected nations. In general, first responders are used to working in their country using the national language, so when interoperability with first responders from a neighbouring country is required, difficulties when speaking in a certain language are faced. In the same way, the information that reaches the population may not be understood if the language differs from the national one. Actions such as the unification of information under a common language, such as English, would not be efficient given the lack of knowledge of the language (especially among the older population) or misunderstanding, which is accentuated in this type of situations involving stress, nervousness or even shock.

G6.3-7 Lack of citizen engagement in Disasters and in risk reduction.

In today's era, information and communication, both between citizens and between states-governments and citizens, has diversified and become more direct.

At a central level, it is observed (for the country of Greece) that efforts are being made to inform the public more generally through various communication channels. The information concerns both safety and protection instructions as well as prevention. But what is missing, at a more specific-local level, is informing citizens about their involvement in an emergency incident. As citizen involvement, we can not only consider the contribution-help with means and resources but the implementation of good practices in order to assist the work of Disaster First Responders.

As a result, information to citizens at the local level is considered as lacking. Citizens are the most significant component of the society, and they are the ones who, with the appropriate guidance and information, have the ability but also the opportunity of assisting in an incident through appropriate actions, pieces of training, guidance documents, communication systems, and more.

Identification of gaps			
Raising practitioner and social awareness			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G6.3-1	Lack of interoperability in communication tools	Professional experience	First responders communicate via various systems and channels. This leads to losing or interrupting information flow
G6.3-2	Hoaxes	Professional experience	Hoaxes are nowadays very popular and social media users often share/post unclear, changed or fake news
G6.3-3	Lack of understanding between agencies	Literature	The major misunderstanding is in terms of current roles and responsibility, including the understanding of each agency's capability and resource
G6.3-4	Alternative communication system	Literature	Destruction of infrastructure such a communication system is critical as well as the lack of coverage. During disaster such as MCI it is necessary to improve agency

Identification of gaps			
Raising practitioner and social awareness			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
			response, especially in terms of communication and reporting lines.
G6.3-5	Lack of public awareness	Literature	Low level of public awareness of the dangers, the possible consequences and readiness for adequate response in early warning and disaster disclosure. The development and implementation of Strategy for public awareness is needed.
G6.3-6	Communication language	Professional experience	Definition of the language in which the authority in charge must notify and inform the population when the MCI takes place in a cross-border region where two or more languages are spoken.
G6.3-7	Lack of citizen engagement in Disasters and in risk reduction	Professional experience	Citizen engagement in Disasters and in risk reduction in a local-municipal level is not available

Table 4 – Gaps from raising practitioner and social awareness

5.4. Civil-Military Cooperation

In the course of the present study, a number of documents, lessons learned and previous operations in response to emergency situations of a regional nature were studied. As a result, some gaps, weaknesses and differences were identified mainly related to civil-military cooperation in case of emergencies.

In general, desk research was conducted, concerning:

- Responsibilities of the institutions regarding crises management and disaster response;
- The obligations of individual institutions related to Crisis management planning process;
- First responders Joint Education and Training;
- The order of action of individual institutions in the implementation of preventive options in response to crises and emergency situations at different levels: Institutional; Municipality; National; Regional; Other;
- The commitments of institutions in Emergency Warning and Disaster Response;
- The capabilities of individual institutions in the Reconnaissance and Observation of the Area of disasters;
- The activation of the teams of individual institution in the Evacuation, search and rescue and medical triage activities;
- The capabilities of individual institutions in helping to restore the social life, public order and Private Security;
- The commitments of the individual institutions related to Disaster relief and Consequence management.

As a result, we classified the discovered gaps and inconsistencies into **different groups**: Legal; Doctrinal; Organizational; Procedural; Technological.

On this basis, it is also possible to arrange by **different levels** - European, national, institutional and regional.

Another possible classification approach is to bring out the problems of interaction **at different stages**: In the Crisis management planning process; In the First responders Joint Education and Training process; During the institutions' response to crises or emergencies.

This can serve as a basis **for identification of the potential areas of collaboration, common effort/possible improvements**. Which would allow defining **areas of mutual interest between military and other actors** in the prevention, preparedness and crises management process.

As a results, the comparative analysis of the disaster response systems and the normative base related to civil-military cooperation and interaction in conditions of large-scale disasters shows that there are significant differences in legislation, preparation, construction and principles of operation.

The issues related to civil-military cooperation in the process of providing assistance to the population under the Civil Protection Mechanism are currently generally complex, with a diverse legal framework, significant differences in the organization, preparation and management of forces and means involved in search and rescue in the disaster area.

A **common weakness** is the fact that in a few countries special legal doctrines, ordinances, rules and procedures have been developed regulating the conditions, the order of introduction, the system of training, command and control and the order of interaction of military teams together with these in the area of the disaster or in the area of the emergency response operation.

There are also **no documents regulating the participation of military formations in the planning of the reaction in case of disasters, in identifying and preparing disaster preventive options and measures**. There are few countries in which training, education and joint exercises are conducted on a single idea, a common scenario and to implement common tasks. The description of this process can be used to create or correct SOP and SOI of formations and in the training of CIMIC specialists.

For example, in Bulgaria there are no plans or programs for joint preparation of the formations of the armed forces with those of the civilian structures and organizations. In practice, joint training programs, joint training and education, exercises and others, which are the basis for building joint capabilities for coordination and interaction are neglected. There is a lack of regulation of the structure, composition, role, tasks, principles and mechanisms of interaction, rules and procedures for activating joint teams, basic requirements and possible joint tasks, scenarios and forms of joint training, command and control, comprehensive support and others.

The same situation is in Hungary, where civil-military cooperation is not found in the programs, courses schedule documents related to the legislation and the documents regulating the responsibilities of the military structures in protecting the population in case of disasters.

In Denmark, the Minister of Defence is the leading figure in the planning and preparation of the structures involved in the emergency response, the armed forces generally do not have a leading role. Nevertheless, they can only be used as a last resort in cases of many casualties and destruction.

In Finland and Greece, the armed forces play an important role in preparing the country for all kinds of disasters and a relatively high share in resolving crises, disasters and other emergencies. At the other pole is Sweden, where the armed forces are not intended to intervene in emergencies, except in extremely complex ones, such as nuclear accidents, disasters and crises at national or international level.

In Germany, army structures intervene only in exceptional cases, at the request of the affected province with a decision at the federal level, but in Slovakia common problems or interoperability gaps are lack of coordination, lack of common protocols, lack of common indexes, lack of common database, lack of common measurable indicators, and lack of specific education. Need of cross-sectorial indicators and common data platform from all sectors would be beneficial, because the actors operate with data coming from different sectors and etc. Education, training and joint preparedness are another problem.

In Spain, the collaboration between Ministry of Defence and civil protection units is articulated either through agreements and conventions established with other bodies of the general administration, or with the autonomous communities, or through the plans. But the problem is a lack of programs for joint exercises, exercises and other forms of building common response capabilities, as well as on the availability of special documents - doctrines, rules and procedures governing civil-military interaction and coordination of efforts between institutions.

G6.4-1: Different scope of civil-military cooperation in EU countries.

In different EU countries, civil-military cooperation differs in content and scope of action. Thus, while in some countries the armed forces only participate in major disasters and the concept of civil-military cooperation is not included in their security strategies, in others, such as Spain, this cooperation is perfectly geared to emergency response.

G6.4-2: Lack of programs and standards for first responders' joint education, training, coaching and exercises.

In some EU countries, there are no adopted programs for joint training on uniform scenarios, common standards and procedures for joint actions of military and civilian teams in cases of natural disasters. The armed forces are not integrated into the emergency response mechanism and are not involved in key aspects of ICM and disaster management such as planning and preparedness. The fact that they are not part of the entire Civil Protection System means that joint civil-military education and training programmes, considered basic and fundamental for an adequate and effective collaboration at the institutional level, are not carried out at the civil-military level. The lack of programs and standards for first responders Joint Education and Training together with those of other teams from other ministries, including military units, reduces overall efficiency and in many cases can lead to confusion, chaos or duplication of effort.

G6.4-3: Lack of protocols for coordination between military and civil actors.

In some countries there are no accepted protocols for joint actions of military and civil teams in cases of disasters. For this reason, there is not and cannot be achieved a sufficiently good coordination between the first rescue teams immediately entering the area of disaster and the previously prepared teams of the armed forces. In addition, they do not have pre-established lines of communication, common capabilities and chain of command.

G6.4-4: Lack of legal procedures for unified planning for joint disaster and emergency operations.

The lack of legal procedures for unified planning for joint reaction in case of disaster and conducting emergency operations is another gap, which leads to inadequate training and preparing of first aid responders and makes it difficult to coordinate actions and synchronize the efforts of different institutions. For this reason, in most countries there are no clear and relevant to modern conditions procedures action plans development.

G6.4-5: Lack of social awareness of the military's involvement and usefulness in the civilian sphere.

Lack of social awareness of the military's involvement and usefulness in the civilian sphere. A large part of society is not aware of how useful the military instrument can be to contribute and help the civilian sphere. Not only to deal with military conflicts of a more violent nature. In this sense, work should be done to give more visibility to the military's contribution to society in this type of catastrophes. As a reference, the support of the military during the pandemic has been very important for the management of this health emergency.

G6.4-6: Lack of political effort to include and develop the military as an instrument of assistance in emergency and civil protection situations.

The lack of political effort to include and develop the military as an instrument of assistance in emergency situations and civil protection. Normalizing the use of the military arm in policy to combat catastrophes, pandemics and natural disasters can be an important step for the civilian sphere to understand its involvement and normalize the processes.

Identification of gaps			
Civil-Military cooperation			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G6.4-1	Different scope of civil-military cooperation in EU countries.	Literature	In some countries, armed forces are only involved in major disasters and do not include the concept of civil-military cooperation in their security strategies.
G6.4-2	Lack of programs and standards for first responders' joint education, training, coaching and exercises	Literature	In most countries, the armed forces are not involved in process of joint education and training on uniform scenarios, common standards and procedures for disaster response planning and preparedness. There is no sharing of training activities or exercises to facilitate the integration of the institutions.
G6.4-3	Lack of protocols for coordination between military and civil actors	Literature	In some countries there are no accepted protocols for joint actions of military and civil teams in cases of disasters

Identification of gaps			
Civil-Military cooperation			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G6.4-4	Lack of legal procedures for unified planning for joint disaster and emergency operations	Literature	In the majority of countries, there are no clear and adequate procedures for developing unified plans for joint actions of teams from different institutions
G6.4-5	Lack of social awareness of the military's involvement and usefulness in the civilian sphere.	Literature	A large part of society is not aware of how useful the military instrument can be in contributing to and assisting the civilian sphere. Not only in dealing with military conflicts of a more violent nature.
G6.4-6	Lack of political effort to include and develop the military as an instrument of assistance in emergency and civil protection situations	Literature	Normalizing the use of the military arm in politics to combat catastrophes, pandemics and natural disasters can be an important step towards the civilian sphere understanding its participation and normalizing processes.

Table 5 – Gaps from civil-military cooperation

5.5. Civil Protection and Aid Volunteerism

G6.5-1: Variability in the mode and degree of cooperation between authorities and civil protection.

There is variability across EU countries in the cooperation between authorities responsible for ICM/disaster management and civil protection. This variability is shown both in the way they cooperate and, in the level, or degree of cooperation. These differences are mainly due to the lack of standardisation in the regulatory bases, the fact that countries have different forms of organisation at the institutional level, as well as the fact that the personnel involved in the different emergency services have different levels of competence.

G6.5-2: No common approach in the post-disaster social and psychosocial support of victims as well as first responders.

Disasters and especially multi-casualty incidents can leave a mark, not only to the victims or relatives of the victims, but also to first responders who engage in response activities and bear witness to extremely stressful situations. One of the main relief activities that are undertaken by agencies and organisations is the post-disaster psychosocial support to both victims and first responders. However, although various mental and psychological relief programmes exist, provided not only by professional first responders' agencies but also from volunteering organisations, there is a need for coordination and collaboration between the aforementioned organisations.

This activity is a strand of the overall response activities, carried out by first responders and could be addressed if a uniform approach was followed for the general coordination between

organisations and agencies. Standardisation could again pave the way. Sakkas et.al. (2020) have documented the lack of a common approach in psychosocial support, in particular, and the difficulties in cooperation between professionals and volunteers due to the fact that different organisations follow different methodologies and have different processes, in general. Although standards related to the management of volunteers exist, e.g., ISO 22319:2017 “Security and resilience – Community resilience – Guidelines for planning the involvement of spontaneous volunteers” and ISO 22395:2018 “Security and resilience – Community resilience – Guidelines for supporting vulnerable persons in an emergency”, there is still a long distance to be covered. A first step could be for organisations to adopt and implement the methodologies proposed by existing standards, whereas the development of new standards could totally address this challenge.

G6.5-3: No clear UCPM cooperation.

When neighbouring countries share common preparedness objectives and regularly conduct joint exercises within the sub-region, collaboration becomes more fluid. While the overarching vision is the desire to increase cooperation between countries, there is no shared understanding in Europe about the limits of civil protection cooperation.

Disaster relief requires short-term availability of personnel and material resources. When situations affect entire regions, cross-border assistance from neighbours is even more necessary in civil protection. The UCPM can support its Member States when they are overwhelmed by an emergency situation, although there is a need to better understand the scenarios in which the UCPM could be activated and what level of response should be expected from the mechanism, as well as the need to develop adequate host country support structures and procedures within its Member States to receive assistance from the UCPM.

G6.5-4: Lack of training on intercultural competences and foreign language skills in organisations active in civil protection.

Organisations active in civil protection face additional challenges due to social and demographic changes. First responders are increasingly confronted with situations that require intercultural competencies and foreign language skills, requiring multicultural teams to act jointly or in a complementary manner in relation to these requirements in disaster situations.

G6.5-5: Insufficient coordination and coherence between national and EU policies.

Insufficient legal preparedness in advance of disasters can slow down the response and waste resources, for example due to overlapping roles and responsibilities of responders. While the European disaster management framework is advanced at regional level, significant legislative preparation remains to be done at national level. The UCPM calls for mutual support and coordination in Europe to respond to disasters.

Consider the legal conditions or protections for disaster responders. Basing oneself solely on the voluntariness of professionals would limit not only their physical but also their legal protection. Considering legal protection both in the exemption of their work activity at the time of the intervention, as well as in legal protection during the intervention or in its consequences (possible injuries, repatriation in case of death or recognition of work activity for the purposes of professional career or working life) would professionalize these actions.

G6.5-6: Integration of volunteers within the response SOP.

Local civil protection services and voluntary organisations involved in civil protection (e.g., volunteer fire brigades, local Red Cross groups, etc.) for common emergencies are key factors in the event of a disaster. They play a vital role throughout the emergency cycle, extending the reach of governments during disasters by providing services they could not otherwise afford, such as 24-hour early warning systems.

It is therefore necessary to create an appropriate organisational and operational framework for volunteering. Volunteers must have a clear and recognised role within the national and local system and a clear legal framework to guarantee their activities is indispensable. It is essential to define the roles of resources according to existing profiles, the chain of command, the liability and the assessment of the necessary logistical arrangements.

G6.5-7: Joint exercises between volunteers and national authorities.

Training more volunteers to mobilise before and during emergencies can reduce risks and damage and help those affected. Experience has confirmed that both local and central preparedness capacities need to be enhanced with qualified staff and volunteers. Regular training and exercises with the different actors involved during an emergency are essential, as is having the right equipment and expertise to deal with new risks. Preparedness must take into account changing risks and learn from past emergencies.

G6.5-8: Insufficient legislation for volunteers.

Volunteer-based organisations must be legally protected and integrated into government actions. Laws and policies affecting volunteers are different in most countries. Government structures need to further integrate such assets into their operational framework, so that these organisations can grow in numbers, strength and competencies. They must also be protected by law, so that they can work with the necessary legal certainty, making the work they do even more valuable.

G6.5-9: Protection of volunteers.

As volunteers are a key actor throughout the emergency cycle, it is vitally important to ensure optimal protection of volunteers during their activity. From a legal point of view, organisations might have to ensure volunteers privately, i.e., by taking out comprehensive insurance.

G6.5-10: No centralised “lessons learned database” for Civil Protection at European level.

Similarly, to the gap G6.2-13 about lessons learned from field exercises in the field of first aid, we could translate the same idea to the civil protection field. UCPM Exchange of Expert programme has standardized reports to compile feedback from past experiences. These reports are not easily accessible and their disseminations is limited.

G6.5-11: Different approach to professional, volunteer first responder teams and spontaneous volunteers.

It is clear that there are extremely wide gaps in management and attitude to ensure different types of approaches of first responders' teams (professionals, volunteers and spontaneous volunteers) on the field and in the training and preparation between different countries.

G6.5-12: Volunteers are not regulated by the law.

In some EU countries the status of Volunteer first responders is not legally regulated. This thing determines difficulties in reconciling this figure and in its appropriate use.

G6.5-13: Volunteers and unified training at National level.

In Greece, volunteer training is carried out by the organization in which each volunteer is a member.

The Fire Service (FS) is the only public authority employing volunteers. In order to bring them to the position of safely and adequately conducting their duties along with the staff of the service, the FS volunteers attend the FS Academy, where newly trained volunteers are accepted twice a year. After their graduation, the new volunteers are allocated to Fire Stations in the Greek region.

In addition, NGOs ought to be operational all year round and act both locally, regionally and nationally, depending on their capacities. They can be activated either at the call of any citizen/private actor in need, according to their expertise but always reporting to the pertinent official governmental authority. Finally, any NGO can be mobilized from any official request of the General Secretariat of Civil Protection (GSCP) or any other government service (e.g., the Coast Guard). In order to be in a position to address these calls, the NGOs' members attend various courses within their own NGO boundaries and receive certifications from third organizations. Apart from these courses, NGO members can attend the FS Academy special training, designated for dedicated types of incidents, such as forest fire prevention and control. According to Hellenic Law 4662/2020 - OGG 27/A/7-2-2020 the framework of voluntarism in Greece is in transition. The mentioned law is in force but is not applied in its entirety yet. Nevertheless, its full application is expected in the near future as soon as all requirements foreseen in it are in place.

According to the provisions of this Law, the GSCP has the steering and coordinating role in Civil Protection training, and prepares all volunteers through courses held in the Academy of Civil Protection. The Academy may enter into Memorandums of Understanding (MoUs), employment agreements, program agreements or contracts with competent public or private bodies, national or supranational, or with other, especially authorized/recognized for this purpose, bodies and institutions, to support its educational purposes.

The Volunteering and Education Directorate of the GSCP is in charge of informing Volunteer Organizations about all types of educational programs. Each volunteer is obliged to receive supplementary training six years after his/her initial acquisition of the volunteering status

As can be easily deduced, there are many things to be aligned, as far as **voluntarism** is concerned. Although the legislation seems to be ready, its implementation still has many steps

ahead. It is extremely hard for the GSCP to be able to evaluate the capacity of all the NGOs when even their training is still left to their own choice and conduction.

Once the law 4662/2020 is fully implemented, the NGOs will be uniformly trained and there will be a distinct and definite level of education, which in turn will create an adequate ground for procedural alignment and improved coordination and it will facilitate the GSCP to be in the position to control the level of volunteers' preparedness and to align their policy and actions, not only among the NGOs but in full compatibility with the state actors.

For the full implementation of the new law, the new Civil Protection Academy, which will undertake the joint training of volunteers, needs to be established first. In addition, the implementation of the individual volunteer ID card needs to be initiated, regardless of the institution to which he/she belongs. Finally, as also foreseen in the new law, all volunteers, who participate in every call for assistance, need to have a new unified operational uniform, with the full implementation of the law.

G6.5-14: International disaster management coordinating organizations must develop a unified/aligned structure for their members' training, processes, and operational procedures.

It is well known that when an EU member-state country facing an incident risk alone are too high, the European Union Civil Protection Mechanism (EUCPM) is activated, at the request of the country facing the incident, and other state members are called for help.

Furthermore, there are occasions in which cross-border operation is required, and the need for at least two states to coordinate is high. In all these cases, the necessity is the same: harmonious operating forces and mechanisms from different nations. The obstacles in these cases overcome the usual difficulties of functionality and coordination of the individual actors, since these actors do not come from a single state and the coordination of their action becomes even more complex. Even if one nation has accomplished an excellent state of operational functionality including all services and stakeholders, the challenge of multi-national performance brings the issue's difficulty to a whole new level.

As (Wasim Shahid, Xinhai, & Muhammad, 2014) have already stated, when people of different origins gather, especially when there is a mutual goal, matters of differences in culture, language, religion, and beliefs are the first to address. Furthermore, when these people have to harmonically operate, matters of variability in operational standards, procedures, skills, experience, tools and technology raise the level of complexity even more. There is often confusion between the organizations when there are no clear roles, no trust concretely built and (Manesh, et al., 2015) the actors' education and training distances the participants from one another furthermore.

Conclusively, international coordinating organizations of disaster management need to formulate a unified/aligned structure of their members' training, processes and operational procedures. A rather constructive suggestion could also be for unified international registration so that a nationally acknowledged member of any GSCP is also visible as a potentially active force on an international level – the EUCPM. Therefore, once a trained volunteer has acquired certified and aligned competencies, it will be feasible for the international coordination centre to know which and how many volunteers can be recruited, where and how. The international registration will, therefore, require a statement of all volunteers' qualifications, regarding every possible aspect, such as experience, prior participation, medical or any kind of training, linguistic skills etc.

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To this point, some of the required steps are already taken. The formation of the EUCPM in 2001, under which GSCPs from 35-member states are coordinated, was the most important step of all.

Nevertheless, the requirements mentioned above are still to be addressed. As far as EUCPM training programs are concerned, they seem to be focused on expert professionals, leaving the volunteers' training section to act as it is nationally (and therefore variously) conducted. There is a small "window frame" for volunteers to be exchanged between organizations, and the project "EU Aid Volunteers (initiated by the European Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations department (DG EAC). Still, volunteers' training and acknowledgement of existence remain mainly the task of each state/nation/organization.

As it is recognized on a national level (for Greece, G6.5-13) the efficiency of volunteers' exploitation on an international level will be respectively elevated if a unified training framework could be adapted in all EUCPM state members, always taking into consideration each country's national characteristics. This has been clearly acknowledged, for example through the Disaster Training Curriculum project, which was funded by the European Union's Seventh Framework Programme. As Khorram-Manesh et. Al (2015) clearly states in their relevant conclusion, after affirming the aforementioned gaps and requirements, "there is an urgent need for a new course in Disaster Management with a modular design to cover all phases of the disaster cycle, to bring different agencies into a common scenario play and to let each organization work within its vertical command based on its traditional or national organizational form while enabling horizontal coordination and communication".

Identification of gaps			
Civil Protection and Aid Volunteerism			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G6.5-1	Variability in the mode and degree of cooperation between authorities and civil protection.	Literature	The variability between the mode and degree of cooperation is due to different normative bases, forms of organisation and levels of competence.
G6.5-2	No common approach in the post-disaster social and psychosocial support of victims as well as first responders.	Literature	Multi-casualty incidents may leave a mark both to the affected populations and first responders, who operate on the field and face stressful situations. Many volunteering organisations provide psychological support to both groups. There is a need for a standardised approach or a widely adopted guideline to this direction.
G6.5-3	No clear UCPM cooperation	Literature	Need to better understand the scenarios in which the UCPM could be activated and what level of response should be expected from the mechanism, as well as the need to develop adequate host country support structures and procedures to receive assistance from UCPM.
G6.5-4	Lack of training on intercultural	Literature	First responders are increasingly confronted with situations that

Identification of gaps			
Civil Protection and Aid Volunteerism			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
	competences and foreign language skills in organisations active in civil protection		require intercultural competencies and foreign language skills, requiring multicultural teams to act jointly or in a complementary manner in relation to these requirements in disaster situations
G6.5-5	Insufficient coordination and coherence between national and EU policies	Literature	While the European disaster management framework is advanced at regional level, significant legislative preparation remains to be done at national level.
G6.5-6	Integration of volunteers within the response SOP	Literature	Volunteers play a vital role throughout the emergency cycle so it is necessary to create an appropriate and recognised organisational and operational framework for volunteering.
G6.5-7	Joint exercises between volunteers and national authorities	Literature	Emergency preparedness capacity needs to be strengthened with qualified staff and volunteers. To this end, it is important that exercises at national and European level include the participation of these volunteers.
G6.5-8	Insufficient legislation for volunteers	Literature	Volunteer based organisations must be protected legally and integrated in government actions.
G6.5-9	Protection of volunteers	Literature	Organisations might need to ensure volunteers privately, i.e., by procuring an all-in insurance
G6.5-10	No centralised “lessons learned database” for Civil Protection at European level	Literature	The dissemination of lessons learned after field exercises and real situations within Europe is limited.
G6.5-11	Different approach to professional, volunteer first responder teams and spontaneous volunteers	Professional experience	Extremely wide gaps in management, attitude to, ensuring of different types of first responders on the field and in the training and preparation.
G6.5-12	Volunteers are not regulated by the law	Professional experience and literature	In some EU countries the status of Volunteer first responders is not legally regulated
G6.5-13	Volunteers and unified training at National level	Professional experience	In Greece, volunteer training is carried out by the organization in which each volunteer is a member.

Identification of gaps			
Civil Protection and Aid Volunteerism			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G6.5-14	International disaster management coordinating organizations must develop a unified/aligned structure for their members' training, processes, and operational procedures.	Professional experience and literature review	Harmonically operating forces and mechanisms from various nations are missing from international disaster management coordinating organisations. As a result, a unified/aligned structure of their members' training, processes, and operational procedures is required.

Table 6 – Gaps from civil protection and aid volunteerism

6. Opportunities

6.1. Task 6.1 Resource federation and trusted information sharing

6.1.1. Data federation between organisations

OP6.1-1: Use of resource federation techniques.

Based on previous gaps indicating that emergency agencies between countries do not employ technological solutions for data federation during cross-border emergency situations, we identify this situation as an opportunity for improvement. Particularly, these countries could benefit for having a common platform at the EU level where they can both initiate an emergent adverse situation and share critical information in real time. Particularly, these solutions should take into consideration essential aspects such as the duration of the data exchange, the permissions that each organisation has to access this information, and the information granularity that each agency require during the emergency.

OP6.1-2: Create a common regulation for resource federation at EU level.

Additionally, there is an opportunity for the definition of a common regulation for resource federation at the EU level, overcoming the barriers of fragmentation that national safeguards may produce. In fact, considering that the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) identifies under the article 9 sub i) a common legal basis for personal data processing, namely if the *“processing is necessary for reasons of public interest in the area of public health, such as protecting against serious cross-border threats to health or ensuring high standards of quality and safety of health care and of medicinal products or medical devices, on the basis of Union or Member State law which provides for suitable and specific measures to safeguard the rights and freedoms of the data subject, in particular professional secrecy”* an effective collaboration between intervening entities on extending the interpretation of this provision could be useful.

OP6.1-3: Dynamic management of data federation.

Furthermore, previous gaps highlight a lack of dynamic management of data federation. To surpass this limitation, the EU could elaborate guidelines with recommendations regarding the best principles to implement dynamic data federation strategies and how to implement them for all EU members. This dynamic behaviour could be beneficial, for example, for ensuring authorised access to intervening entities during the emergency, revoking the access to that data afterwards, when it is not needed.

OP6.1-14: Federation incompatibilities.

Regarding data federation technologies, and although some of them present incompatibilities, EU regulations could offer recommendations on which technologies are more suitable for addressing cross-border data federation. If these regulations are implemented by all EU members and organisations within them, this could potentially solve these incompatibilities.

OP6.1-15: OAuth 2.0 – Optimised designs for data federation.

Focusing on particular federation technologies and protocols, the complexity of OAuth when a substantial number of members intervene generates an opportunity for system administrators to design federated systems with a low structural complexity. This optimisation of resources is essential in large scale scenarios as the one introduced by Valkyries.

OP6.1-16: OAuth 2.0 – Redundant authorisation server.

Furthermore, the gap of OAuth in which the authorisation server could be a single point of failure against attacks could be easily surpassed by using load balancing techniques. In this sense, all access to the authorisation server would go through the load balancing, which would prevent attackers to overload the server.

OP6.1-17: Shibboleth – Sign Out.

Another relevant technology for data federation between first responders is Shibboleth. Its limitation concerning the inability to perform a single sign out could be surpassed by contributing to the Shibboleth standard, thus providing this functionality in the near future.

OP6.1-18: Shibboleth – Reduce implementation complexity.

The complexity of proxy servers could also be an interesting point to provide improvements for the Shibboleth standard.

6.1.2. Mechanism to provide data confidentiality**OP6.1-4: Use of temporal session keys.**

Based on the previous gaps related to the data confidentiality that warn about the threats that the current confidentiality mechanisms may face in the near future, some opportunities have been identified to face them. Furthermore, as the use of pre-shared keys is discouraged, as it was described in G6.1-6, this describes the opportunity to use temporary keys to protect the communications, as it would reduce considerably the impact of an attack.

OP6.1-5: Generate a certification authority at EU level for emergencies

The definition of a common European certification authority for emergencies could be use useful to simplify the complexity of public key infrastructures required in these scenarios. Moreover, it could provide a simpler scenario for emergency agencies to better improve the security of their technological solutions.

6.1.3. Mechanism to provide resource integrity

Based on the previous gaps related to the data integrity risks and needs, some opportunities were identified:

OP6.1-7: Optimisation of data redundancy techniques regarding data storage.

Regarding data redundancy, there is an opportunity to optimise the protocols and techniques used for data storage, to improve their efficiency regarding storage resources.

OP6.1-8: Optimisation of data redundancy techniques regarding data coherence.

Furthermore, these techniques could also be improved regarding data coherence between nodes.

OP6.1-9: EU regulations regarding data redundancy.

EU members could define new regulations concerning data redundancy, making efforts to create guidelines or regulations offering recommendations about suitable technologies to avoid the limitations of data redundancy previously presented.

OP6.1-24: Common data language, taxonomy and reference schema

To support a dynamic and multi-event common data referential, covering the needs of the topology, data language, etc., a dynamic library can be established to provides the function to store the different data schemas, and provide the tools to define new data schemas, and makes them public for any Emergency event being deployed.

OP6.1-25: Tampered data

To account for the trust of the data, the use of Blockchain enables the increase of the data trustfulness by enabling the detection and identification of tampered data. The blockchain can also record all metadata of the shared data, allowing the traceability and auditing for the data usage and for unauthorized data usage and access.

OP6.1-26: COP marking data source

There is also an opportunity to explore the use of COP marking external vs own data sources in order to improve the awareness and context of data usage, by clearly displaying icons that identify which is data from the entity own sources and which are provided by external sources.

OP6.1-27: Backup data

Support data integrity by establishing a networks of backup services to record and restore data: Blockchain services to store transactional data and metadata, and other servers to store and recover: the data stream, non-transactional and documents shared. To reinforce the resilience of the application in the case of connectivity loss to the SIGRUN backup servers, a local capability could be locally supported and resync after reconnection is established with serves.

6.1.4. Mechanism to provide availability of the collaboration**OP6.1-10: Dynamic network management**

Emergency agencies could employ dynamic network approaches to prevent communication systems to be static, thus offering reconfiguration capabilities that could be useful in disaster scenarios where part of the network becomes inoperative. Thus, approaches such as software defined networks (or SDN) could be of great help to offer adaptability and better services, also reducing the cost of maintaining the network.

OP6.1-11: On-demand security capabilities

There is an opportunity for EU regulation providing insights regarding how to manage emergency networks dynamically, able to reconfigure on demand based on different criteria. For example, they could be adapted to be more efficient or dimensioned to support an increase of communication flows. Moreover, this dynamic behaviour allows deploying on-demand security capabilities according to the current networks and the existence of previously detected risks or threats.

Based on the frameworks that will be used, there is a need for a mechanism to support collaboration through the course of the system. We must define the factors to support these mechanisms. Factors such as

1. Information Availability
2. Actions needed
3. Multi users and interfaces

Each of these factors is taken into consideration in order to perform collaboration among multiple users and interactions. We need to specify specific actions to be taken for the information to be available at any given point in time. That information will work as a method to learning a new process or how to collaborate with other partners and share knowledge between multiple parties.

Sharing resources and ideas will establish a common ground in order for new collaboration mechanism to be built upon.

There must be a framework of actions allowed in order to mature the common idea of collaboration. Thus, in that way of producing and maturing new ways of cooperation, overcoming diversity and applying a common governance policy.

Very important is to avoid conflicts between and action is the key to success.

Each case is unique. Design, operational and learning practices in order to develop and enhance an inquiring system of collaboration.

We could consider the possibility of creating a collaboration toolbox so that to create new opportunities, fundamentals and how mistakes to be avoided in future references.

In doing so we are building trustworthiness between parties, commitment and providing the right tools for all the operations to function upon demand and at any given timeframe.

OP6.1-29 Information integration

Have or create a framework that integrates the information and specific requirements currently in order to harmonize an integrating solution with a focus on international collaboration and be a solution to the actions of the current scope.

6.1.5. Frameworks offering data federation

OP6.1-12: EU Regulations regarding data federation framework.

The frameworks offering data federation are developed by the organisations and cannot be used by all participants in emergencies. The different frameworks of the individual organisations work in different ways. This situation creates a coordination problem due to the interoperability between platforms. A common framework would be desirable. For this, it would be necessary to establish regulations at European level to encourage the organisation to adapt to this common framework.

OP6.1-13: Definition of general data federation frameworks.

The frameworks created by each of the organisations are highly specific and technical as they were created for a specific purpose. These specific frameworks do not have functionalities required to manage and lead the emergency at a general level. To lead emergency management, not much specific data is needed. Simplified data that represents resources and needs in real time is needed for management. This information would be obtained from different sources. Therefore, a general framework focused on emergency management with simple and useful data would be desirable.

Additionally, organisations involved in emergency management use their own frameworks. These own frameworks are often not interoperable with other organisations frameworks. Then, they do not share or receive data. The information that is shared between organisations may be via radio or telephone, with unsystematic and underdeveloped methods. For all these reasons, a common frame of reference would be desirable, able to collect information from the emergency partners own frameworks. This data would be processed based on a common reference and translated into different languages and international systems (metric, temperature, speed, etc.), as highlighted by OP6.1-28. This would ensure full interoperability between the own frameworks without changes to the own frameworks.

OP6.1-19 & OP6.1-20: PQC KEM hybrid schemas & PQC DSA hybrid schemas.

Regarding the quantum threat, three opportunities have been identified. The OP6.1-19 and OP6.1-20 address the opportunity to implement Hybrid PQC schemes, which means to add a PQC security layer to the current cryptosystems; particularly, the OP6.1-21 focuses on the confidentiality and the encryption while the OP6.1-22 focuses on the digital signatures, strictly related to de integrity and authenticity of the information.

OP6.1-6: Use of hybrid cryptographic solutions.

This opportunity also addresses the opportunity to use hybrid schemas, focusing on the combination of symmetric and asymmetric cryptography, which could be uses in different phases.

OP6.1-21: Quantum Key Distribution.

On the other hand, regarding to the secure key distribution, the OP6.1-21 focuses on the secure QKD, which provides theoretically secure key distribution to the system.

OP6.1-22: Light cryptographic methods.

Related to the previous opportunities, this opportunity (related to OP6.1-19 and OP6.1-20) suggests using lightweight cryptography, as some mechanisms require less computational cost while providing enough security to a system that involves less powerful or degraded devices.

OP6.1-23: Distributed PKI.

In order to assure the availability of the PKI during an emergency actuation, this opportunity addresses the use distributed key distribution infrastructure to avoid the threat of network failures and PKI unavailability, which can be related to the use of QKD.

OP6.1-28: Valkyries framework

Create a framework that responds to a standard of needs and guarantees the protection and access to information through the application of recognized standards.

OP6.1-30: Protocol of use and development

Development of protocols and user manuals for all types of roles and responsibilities for the new framework. Identification of information elements and their applications for future developments.

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Opportunities			
Resource Federation and trusted information sharing			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP6.1-1	G6.1-1 G6.1-2 G6.1-3	Use of resource federation techniques	The Valkyries project identifies an opportunity for implementing data federation and data sharing strategies between EU members in emergency situations.
OP6.1-2	G6.1-4	Create a common regulation for resource federation at the EU level	Creating a new EU-level federation regulation could allow countries to effectively share sensitive data between affected members following GDPR guidelines.
OP6.1-3	G6.1-4 G6.1-5	Dynamic management of data federation	The EU could define guidelines indicating the best principles to implement dynamic data federation strategies, as well as creating regulations for their implantation for all EU members.
OP6.1-4	G6.1-6	Use of temporal session keys	Since using pre-shared keys for protecting communications is not recommended, we encourage as an opportunity for improvement the use of temporal keys derived from an initial key, reducing the impact of attacks on confidentiality.
OP6.1-5	G6.1-7	Generate a certification authority at EU level for emergencies	The creation of a certification authority at EU level for its use in emergency situations could considerably simplify the complexity of the public key infrastructure required in these scenarios.
OP6.1-6	G6.1-8	Use of hybrid cryptographic solutions	In practise, applications commonly use a hybrid approach between symmetric and asymmetric cryptography. The first one is used for encrypting the data transmitted, while the latter is employed for key distribution. There is an opportunity for standardisation in this regard at EU level, particularly in medical scenarios, and for the use of Decentralized identifiers and verifiable credentials.
OP6.1-7	G6.1-9 G6.1-10 G6.1-11	Optimisation of data redundancy techniques regarding data storage	There is an opportunity for improving the efficiency of protocols and techniques used for data redundancy, optimising storage resources.
OP6.1-8	G6.1-10 G6.1-11	Optimisation of data redundancy techniques regarding data coherence	There is an opportunity for improving current protocols and techniques used for data redundancy, taking into consideration data coherence between nodes.

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Opportunities			
Resource Federation and trusted information sharing			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP6.1-9	G6.1-9 G6.1-10 G6.1-11	EU regulations regarding data redundancy	The EU could put efforts in creating guidelines or regulations offering recommendations about the most suitable technologies to avoid these situations.
OP6.1-10	G6.1-12	Dynamic network management	Emergency services could benefit from using dynamic network management principles such as SDN to reconfigure the network to offer more adaptability and better services, reducing the cost.
OP6.1-11	G6.1-13	On-demand security capabilities	There is room for regulations indicating how to manage emergency networks in a dynamic way to offer security capabilities on demand.
OP6.1-12	G6.1-14 G6.1-15	EU Regulations regarding data federation framework	It would be desirable that all EU members adopt a common framework offering data federation. Therefore, it is necessary to establish regulations, with respect to data federation and frameworks.
OP6.1-13	G6.1-14 G6.1-15	Definition of general data federation frameworks	There is an opportunity for designing and creating a general enough framework to include all particularities of the different emergency services operating in the EU.
OP6.1-14	G6.1-14 G6.1-15 G6.1-16	Federation incompatibilities	EU regulations could offer a list of federation technologies that should be implemented by all federation platforms and technologies to comply with the EU regulation.
OP6.1-15	G6.1-17	OAuth 2.0 - Optimised designs for data federations	There is an opportunity for system administrators to design federated systems keeping a low structural complexity.
OP6.1-16	G6.1-18	OAuth 2.0 - Redundant authorisation server	There is an opportunity for system administrators to design federated systems based on OAuth using load balancing techniques over multiple authorisation servers.
OP6.1-17	G6.1-19	Shibboleth - Single Sign Out	Valkyries identifies an opportunity to improve the Shibboleth standard by incorporating single sign out capabilities.
OP6.1-18	G6.1-20	Shibboleth - Reduce implementation complexity	There is an opportunity for improving the Shibboleth standard to ease the complexity of proxy servers.
OP6.1-19	G6.1-21, G6.1-22	PQC KEM hybrid schemas	As PQC standardization enables to implement efficient cypher cryptosystems, there is an opportunity to implement these schemas and avoid future transitions.

Opportunities			
Resource Federation and trusted information sharing			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP6.1-20	G6.1-21, G6.1-22	PQC DSA hybrid schemas	As PQC standardization enables to implement efficient signature cryptosystems, there is an opportunity to implement these schemas and avoid future transitions.
OP6.1-21	G6.1-21, G6.1-23	Quantum Key Distribution	The implementation of QKD systems would provide information-theoretically secure keys to the cryptosystem.
OP6.1-22	G6.1-22, G6.1-24	Light cryptographic methods	The use of lighter algorithms will ease the <u>implementation</u> using less powerful devices.
OP6.1-23	G6.1-23, G6.1-25	Distributed PKI	The use of distributed PKI would avoid the problems of availability related to network failures during emergency actuations.
OP6.1-24	G6.1-26, G6.1-27, G6.1-29	Common data language, taxonomy and reference schema	Use of a scheme Library supported on a database, where the library holds different cooperation reference schemas allows each event to negotiate establish and store the schema used by the event, or reuse in future events. It enables a federated system to define a common reference frame for data sharing
OP6.1-25	G6.1-28	Tampered data	Use of Blockchain to detect tampered data and data auditing
OP6.1-26	G6.1-30	COP marking data source	Establish a COP definition to mark differently external and own data sources displayed
OP6.1-27	G6.1-31	Backup data	Define a backup service to collect all the data: Blockchain for transactional data, and for all the exchanged metadata. Local data backup capability to provide resilience and adaptability in case of connectivity lost. Establish an automatic restore capability in case of temporary data lost
OP6.1-28	G6.1-33	Valkyries framework	Define a high-level framework that translates de data and make this interoperable (SIGRUN).
OP6.1-29	G6.1-34	Information integration	Collect reliable minimum requirements
OP6.1-30	G6.1-35	Protocol of use and development	Declaration of useful information for development and use of the framework

Table 7 – Opportunities from Task 6.1 Resource Federation and trusted information sharing

6.2. Task 6.2 Education and training for first aid responses

OP6.2-1: Common core curriculum for the speciality of emergency medicine.

The speciality of emergency medicine is not recognised in all EU countries. A common core curriculum could be used as a basis for the implementation of this speciality. In this respect, the WHO provides a classification and minimum standards for emergency medical teams, which could serve as a basis for a European classification. The European Medical Corps initiative in the framework of the European Civil Protection Mechanism is in line with the WHO roadmap for EMTs and meets high standards, including those internationally recognised by the WHO where they exist. According to this classification, first responders intervening in an MCI or disaster could be equated to mobile EMT-Type 1.

OP6.2-2: European Paramedic Curriculum (EPaCur).

Paramedic training varies in different EU countries and there is a growing need for this type of professional profile with a high level of training. While it should be borne in mind that countries may have different operational procedures for ICM and disaster response and different training curricula, a standardised curriculum at European level could facilitate their homogenisation. Such a curriculum could increase the number of countries offering this type of training at the undergraduate level, which would raise the level of competence of paramedical professionals in general.

OP6.2-3: Cooperation and coordination between institutions.

One of the deficiencies detected in ICM and disaster management in the different EU countries is the lack of cooperation and coordination between institutions. In addition to the lack of procedures to facilitate cross-sectoral and cross-border cooperation, there is a lack of tools for information exchange. This exchange is vital for decision-making, but the institutions must define the data that are relevant and necessary for management in their sphere of action.

OP6.2-4: Standardisation of reports and debriefing.

Debriefing reports after a cross-border MCI (real or as part of a field exercise) help to identify what has worked well and how practices can be institutionalised, and what has not worked and requires corrective action. Standardising the data collected would facilitate the compilation of the information and its analysis to improve response, giving recommendations directed to decision-makers. The implementation of the debriefing standardised reports could be based in the EU Civil Protection Knowledge Network and Lessons Learned Programme , Exchange of Experts Programme or WHO Guidance for After Action Review .

OP6.2-5: Creation of a UCPM Lessons Learnt database for FARs at European level.

The creation of a global lessons learned database for FARs with the standardised outcomes from debriefing reports would make easier to identify practices that could be institutionalised and procedures that requires corrective action to improve from past experiences the response and preparedness to cross-border MCI emergencies. The development of such a database could promote transparency and collective learning among countries, thereby strengthening preparedness and response at the global level.

OP6.2-6: Creation of a universally valid European First Aid Certificates.

Regarding the lack of universally valid of a European First Aid Certificate to guarantees a minimum knowledge base in first aid at European level is hard to be solve at this stage, as it would require political action by the European Union and its Member States. Anyway, the training to get this kind of certificate should be recognised via the European Qualification Framework (EQF) and be conducted by the European Agency for Health and Safety at Work (EU-OSHA), based on the guidelines of the European Resuscitation Council (ERC).

OP6.2-7: Creation of a Register of European First Aid members.

The creation of a Register of European First Aid members would allow the standardization of intervention protocols in Mass Casualty Incident (MCI), optimize the resources available in each country and improve coordination in cross-border incidents.

OP6.2-8: Conduct of simulation exercises /OP6.2-9: Creating or supplementing the legislative framework in the field of natural disasters and environmental catastrophes.

Creating or supplementing the legislative framework in the field of natural disasters and environmental catastrophes is imperative from the point of view of refining the conceptual apparatus because the declaration of a state of emergency requires the existence of a law defining extraordinary events. According to the European and national legislation, must be defined clearly and motivated whether natural disasters and environmental catastrophes are extraordinary events or at a certain point in their development they grow into such. This will make it possible not to have to make frequent changes in the organization of the legal and management policy upon the occurrence of these events, as well as resource planning as they arise.

OP6.2-10: Development and testing of Joint multination training for first responders. The implementation of this opportunity will provide Joint multination training for first responders (EMS, FRS, Police, etc.) that would serve as a basis for improvement the efficiency into MCI management. The training would include: First, knowledge and skills of the First responders from different EU MS and to be able to work together in a more effective way. Second, in addition to the knowledge on basic medical topics, the training should provide knowledge of disaster management principles (command, control, communication, coordination and collaboration). Finally, online and hands-on training would help the trainees to use the new technological solutions for digitalisation of the existing procedures and data exchange.

Opportunities			
Education and training for first aid responses			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP6.2-1	G6.2-3	Common core curriculum for the speciality of emergency medicine	The WHO provides a classification and minimum standards for emergency medical teams that could serve as a basis for a European classification.
OP6.2-2	G6.2-1, G6.2-5	European Paramedic Curriculum (EPaCur)	This curriculum could increase the number of countries offering this type of training at the undergraduate level, which would raise the level of

Opportunities			
Education and training for first aid responses			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
			competence of paramedical professionals in general.
OP6.2-3	G6.2-8	Cooperation and coordination between institutions	Facilitate the exchange of information necessary for decision-making by the different services involved in the emergency response.
OP6.2-4	G6.2-9	Standardisation of reports, debriefing and post disaster psychological support.	Implementation of a system based on the EU Civil Protection Knowledge Network and Lessons Learned Programme or WHO Guidance for After Action Review. Standardised data collection could facilitate the compilation of the information in a global database.
OP6.2-5	G6.2-21	Creation of a UCPM Lessons Learnt data base at the European level	A global database of lessons learned would connect outcomes that could be transformed into recommendations for future improvement.
OP6.2-6	G6.2-2	Creation of a universally valid European First Aid Certificates	These certificates should be issued by a National accredited institution after a specific training recognised via EQF and be conducted by the EU-OSHA, based on the guidelines of the ERC.
OP6.2-7	G.6.2-22	Creation of a Register of European First Aid members.	A European First Aid Certificate opens the opportunity to create a European register of qualified personnel for the intervention in Mass Casualty Incident (MCI). These types of registries help the development of international and cross-border protocols.
OP6.2-8	G6.2-10 G6.2-11	Conduct of simulation exercises	Development of educational software for simulations of disasters, accidents and catastrophes for educational purposes. The software, in this sense, will contribute to the quality and effect of the overall training process in the direction of forming and upgrading the practical skills of employees for risk assessment, timely management decision-making, ensuring appropriate coordination, and emergency control and response systems situations. The purpose of its development is for every employee of the FARs to be registered in the specified

Opportunities			
Education and training for first aid responses			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
			platform and to have access to training materials for various courses.
OP6.2-9	G6.2-10 G6.2-11	Creating or supplementing the legislative framework in the field of natural disasters and environmental catastrophes.	Development of educational software for This initiative is imperative from the point of view of refining the conceptual apparatus, because the declaration of a state of emergency requires the existence of a law defining extraordinary events.
OP6.2-10	G6.2-11 G6.2-13 G6.2-22	Joint multinational training for first responders	Joint multinational training for first responders (EMS, FRS, Police, etc.) would bring more efficiency into MCI management. This would align the level of knowledge and skills of the First responders from different EU MS and they would be able to work in a more effective way. Besides, the knowledge on medical topics, the training should provide knowledge of disaster management principles, such as command, control, communication, coordination and collaboration. Finally, online and hands-on training is needed about how to use the new technological solutions.

Table 7 – Opportunities from education and training for first aid responses

6.3. Raising practitioner and social awareness

OP6.3-1: SIGRUN application.

SIGRUN will reference harmonize and integrate some of the analysed opportunities towards delivering a cognitive communications and resource federation platform for C&C at first aid responses in MCI. Among others, SIGRUN will include tactical command and control systems and services, and a mobile application able to public alerting/warning and crowdsourcing a common operational picture.

OP6.3-2: VOSTs.

VOSTs are support units in disaster management that can generate additional information for crisis teams, decision-makers and authorities by sifting through the usual flood of data for relevant information in the event of a crisis or disaster. After the triumph of online networks and mobile internet, the flood of available information proved almost impossible to keep track of. VOSTs employ experts who not only feel at home in the field of social networks and internet technologies but also have experience in disaster management. Another advantage: crisis teams and decision-makers can access additional information without having to plan their own personnel capacities. The detection of fake news and disinformation on the internet is one of the core tasks of a VOST. Ideally, such fake news is identified at an early stage and transmitted

to the client (e.g., a health authority) so that the latter can debunk the disinformation in its own public relations work. Here, a VOST can also be supportive and assist the authority in communicating through its own network. Another advantage is that VOSTs are closely networked within Europe and worldwide and are in constant exchange. In this way, fake news can sometimes be identified before they circulate on the networks in their own national language.

The past has also shown that in resilient societies, groups emerge during crises and disasters to offer support and help. As they often organise themselves through social networks, identifying them through a VOST can provide helpful information to governmental structures or local authorities about additional resources available to support the regularly alerted responders. At the same time, a VOST would be able to identify needs expressed in the respective social networks in order to support the responsible crisis team in decision-making or prioritisation.

OP6.3-3: Debriefing sessions after each incident or disaster.

Debriefing sessions held after the incident or disaster should play a significant role. First responders and all involved units and services need to be informed about all fact which during the intervention were good or bad organised. There is a space for identifying strengths and weaknesses. First responders as each service separately and as a whole system of organisations need to gather and exchange good or even bad practices from the intervention and apply them in future incidents or emergency response.

OP6.3-4: Alternative communication system.

Communication during and immediately after a disaster situation is a vital component of response and recovery. Effective communication connects first responders, support systems, and family members with the communities and individuals immersed in the disaster.

During a disaster, it is important to have alternative methods of communication. Providing communication as part of a disaster plan, as well as utilizing ham radio, social networking sites and emergency alert systems, are alternative ways to communicate during a disaster.

Alternative communication modes (that can be activated after the failure of normally used equipment which becomes broken after damaging communications infrastructure near the place of incident or disaster) can be infrastructure independent (short wave radio, two-way radio, weather radio ...) or infrastructure dependent (LED electronic signs, digital signage ...).

Emergencies place demand on communication processes that are often significantly different from the demands of non-emergency circumstances. Emergency communication systems often provide or integrate those same notification services but will also include two-way communications typically to facilitate communications between emergency communication staff, affected people and first responders in field.

Suggestion not using and avoid using alternative non-EU systems after the collapse of the original communication, because those communications for example GLONASS, are compromised, because of the hostile intentions of Russia toward Ukraine and the EU as a whole, circumstantially in extension. This also goes toward the Chinese systems for communication, because of their hostile actions against Taiwan, aka Republic of China. Those arguments can be reinforced with the growing tensions and the ongoing stand-off between Russia and the EU and probably the common Russian-Chinese projects, such as the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO), One Belt-One Road (OBOR) and BRICS hiddenly pointed towards the hindrance to Europe. It is like an invisible menace or even a threat towards the whole continent and especially indirect

to Eastern and probably Central Europe. Based on the contemporary geopolitical situation the avoidance of non-EU systems for communications and sharing information on their channels in case of break of communications between the EU members is a vital for their preservation and the same thing of the EU sovereignty.

OP6.3-5: Strategy for public awareness.

The strategy must include information about priority target groups; key to the public awareness messages in connection with the dangers; methods of conveying the messages to different target groups – through existing networks suitable media and other means; methods of evaluation / monitoring of public awareness and readiness; resources, materials, etc.; the implementation of monitoring and reporting on the progress of the strategy for public awareness. Develop and regularly update the website of the regional administration of relevant information about hazards and related preparedness measures.

At the national level, it is noticed (for Greece) that attempts are being made to enlighten the public more broadly through various communication channels. The material includes advice for safety and protection as well as prevention. However, at a more specific-local level, residents are not informed about their engagement in an emergency occurrence.

The opportunity identified is the creation of a "local-municipal" portal. Through this, the Municipalities/Communities will be able to have a complete picture of the citizens who live in the area, but also whether they have any expertise in a field that can contribute in an emergency.

Essentially, in the already existing account that each citizen already has, and is accessible only through the single portal of the General Information Systems of the State (Hellenic Republic), he will be able to enter a special tab (e.g., personal information) the certifications that have for corresponding cases (e.g., certification in CPR and trauma treatment).

Having this information, the Municipalities/Communities will be able to send notifications to the respective users with one click.

The whole process will be able to be used at the central or regional level, beyond the municipal/community level, as the information will be provided through/to the single portal of Greece.

OP6.3-6: Unified communication language.

As part of the harmonization proposals and given that the use of a unified common language for several countries does not seem possible in many cases, the analysis of the signalling and citizen information systems used in each country of the European Union gains a great importance. The detection of current and the proposal of new common nomenclatures, indicative signs, warning systems or colour codes that allow the population to be informed of the disaster that has taken place and possible replicas or chain events, as well as the indications of the security protocols to follow represent a clear opportunity for the project that responds to the G6.3-6 detected.

OP6.3-7: Improvement of citizens' engagement in crisis management at local level

At the national level, it is noticed (for Greece) that attempts are being made to enlighten the public more broadly through various communication channels. The material includes advice for safety and protection as well as prevention. However, at a more specific-local level, residents are not informed about their engagement in an emergency occurrence.

The opportunity identified is the creation of a "local-municipal" portal. Through this, the Municipalities/Communities will be able to have a complete picture of the citizens who live in the area, but also whether they have any expertise in a field that can contribute in an emergency.

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Having this information, the Municipalities/Communities will be able to send notifications to the respective users with one click.

The whole process will be able to be used at the central or regional level, beyond the municipal/community level, as the information will be provided through/to the single portal of Greece.

Opportunities			
Raising practitioner and social awareness			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP6.3-1	G6.3-1	SIGRUN application	Providing advanced communications, information sharing and tactical C&C services for the first (first-aid) responders
OP6.3-2	G6.3-2	VOSTs	Virtual Operation Support Teams (VOSTs) have been established in many countries to help authorities manage information in high-pressure information environments. These teams monitor social media, support situational awareness, counter rumours and disseminate official communication. Establishing this kind of teams within all EU countries.
OP6.3-3	G6.3-3	Debriefing sessions after each incident or disaster	This is an issue that also arise in D5.2. Debriefing sessions after the intervention are missing or unappreciated parts of the incident or disaster
OP6.3-4	G6.3-4	Alternative communication system	Provide the back-up plan in the case of failure of ordinary used systems
OP6.3-5	G6.3-5	Strategy for rising of public awareness in Multi Casualty Incidents	Development and implementation of a Strategy for rising of public awareness in Multi Casualty Incidents. Establish a local portal of "local champions/ certified citizens ready to help".
OP6.3-6	G6.3-6	Unified communication language	Design of a catalogue of visual warning signs (indicative signs, colour codes) or auditory signs (alarms) to alert and inform the population.
OP6.3-7	G6.3-7	Improvement of citizen engagement in crisis	Establish a local portal of "local champions/ certified citizens ready to help"

Opportunities			
Raising practitioner and social awareness			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
		management at local level	

Table 8 – Opportunities from raising practitioner and social awareness

6.4. Civil-Military cooperation

It is very important to develop some opportunities/possibilities for harmonization opportunities on the preparedness and cross-sectorial collaboration for first aid response to multi-casualty disasters

These possibilities/opportunities should be aimed for enhancing mutual capabilities in the prevention, preparedness and crises management process in the scope of cross-institutional cooperation.

The need for clear procedures, standards and rules for the use of armed forces in support of civilians in disasters with mass casualties and destruction is clearly visible.

Procedures for such participation should be developed through guidelines (recommendations) to be issued by introducing changes (corrections to existing) or new procedures.

A very important area is also the development of a common legal framework to regulate the rights and responsibilities of the various participants in the operation in the disaster zone, as well as uniform training scenarios, common tasks and uniform principles and mechanisms for management.

Once again, we believe that the **main directions of work** in this area are:

- Creating unity of action and unity of efforts during the planning process
- Building a single database of functional specialists
- Joint preparation to a single plan and scenario
- Development standards determined on the basis of the analysis and practical application of joint procedures
- **At national level** - the commissions and centres should recommend the implementation and further development of national requirements and capabilities for the implementation of joint civil-military procedures for disasters, accidents and catastrophes
- **At the tactical level** - to appoint and train joint civil-military teams to start the application of the procedures developed and proposed for practical implementation

And also, sharing lessons learned from CIMIC practice can help to develop more effective ways to improve, implement and transform CIMIC capabilities.

OP6.4-1: Implementation of European civil-military doctrine.

At the EU level there is no standardisation in civil-military cooperation. However, at the European level the Joint Allied Doctrine for the Military Contribution to Humanitarian Assistance has been developed. This doctrine provides basic guidelines and standards for the planning and execution of operations in support of civilian structures. The application of this doctrine in

individual countries would facilitate a homogenous system of civil-military cooperation. There is also a training centre where formal training could be provided.

OP6.4-2: Shared understanding brought about by working together, connecting and education.

Through creation and adoption of unified guidance, procedures and TTPs for applying the capabilities of CIMIC specialists and experts in disaster settings will provide greater clarity on the contribution and future actions of civil and military actors in such operations. All this can lead to a unified understanding of the situation, the necessary actions and shared responsibilities between the teams of first aid responders.

OP6.4-3: Development of national requirements and capabilities for the implementation of joint civil-military procedures for disasters, accidents and catastrophes.

By developing national requirements and a program to build capabilities to implement joint civil-military procedures in disasters, accidents and catastrophes, better coordination and cooperation between military and civilian teams will be achieved. Thereby building common procedures, standards and national and Union capabilities for effective response to natural disasters with mass casualties and destruction.

OP6.4-4: Programs and scenarios for joint training of civil-military teams developing.

Programs and scenarios for joint training of civil-military teams should be developed. If programs and scenarios are developed for the joint training of civil-military teams, then in cases of natural disasters, they will immediately begin the implementation of the developed and mastered practical procedures for providing assistance to the population.

OP6.4-5: Conduct active outreach to raise awareness of the benefits of military involvement in catastrophic disasters.

A large part of society is not aware of how useful the military instrument can be in contributing to and assisting the civilian sphere. For this reason conducting active outreach to raise awareness of the benefits of military involvement in catastrophic disasters is a vital opportunity.

OP6.4-6: Insertion of new technology, communications and data exchanging planform within the EU countries.

Introducing new technologies and lines of communication between countries within the EU, building a common platform for monitoring, warning, data exchange and sharing the Common Operational Picture (COP) of the disaster area in real time.

Opportunities			
Civil-Military cooperation			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP6.4-1	G6.4-1, G6.4-2	Implementation of European Civil-Military Doctrine	At the European level, the Joint Allied Doctrine for the Military Contribution to Humanitarian Assistance has been developed to provide basic guidelines and standards for planning and executing operations in support of civilian structures. There is also a training centre.

Opportunities			
Civil-Military cooperation			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP6.4-2	G6.4-3	Shared understanding brought about by working together, connecting, education	Through creation and adoption of unified guidance, procedures and TTPs for applying the capabilities of CIMIC specialists and experts in disaster settings will provide greater clarity on the contribution and future actions of civil and military actors in such operations.
OP6.4-3	G6.4-4, G6.4-8	Development of national requirements and capabilities for the implementation of joint civil-military procedures for disasters, accidents and catastrophes	By developing national requirements and a program to build capabilities to implement joint civil-military procedures in disasters, accidents and catastrophes, better coordination and cooperation between military and civilian teams will be achieved.
OP6.4-4	G-6.4-5	Plans, programs and scenarios for joint training of civil-military teams developing	If plans, programs and scenarios are common developed for the joint training of civil-military teams, then in cases of natural disasters, they will immediately begin the implementation of the developed and mastered practical procedures for providing assistance to the population.
OP6.4-5	G-6.4-7	Conduct active outreach to raise awareness of the benefits of military involvement in catastrophic disasters	A large part of society is not aware of how useful the military instrument can be in contributing to and assisting the civilian sphere. For this reason conducting active outreach to raise awareness of the benefits of military involvement in catastrophic disasters is a vital opportunity.
OP6.4-6	G6.4-6	Insertion of new technology, communications and data exchanging platform within the EU countries	Introducing new technologies and lines of communication between countries within the EU, building a common platform for warning, data exchange and sharing of the Common Operational Picture (COP) of the disaster area.

Table 9 – Opportunities from civil-military cooperation

6.5. Civil Protection and Aid Volunteerism

OP6.5-1: Encourage the intercultural competencies and foreign language skills in the training for first responders to cross-border MCI.

To be prepared for a coordinated emergency response, the various disaster management actors need to be aware of each other's systems, working structures, guidelines and standard operating procedures. Joint organisation and mutual participation in each other's training and exercises, as well as investment in inter-agency cooperation - including by inviting civil society

representatives to civil protection coordination bodies at different levels - are useful to expand this knowledge.

In addition, successful coordination during cross-border MCI relies not only on clear and well described operational procedures, but also on appropriate joint trainings that should also include intercultural competencies and foreign language skills.

OP6.5-2: Integration of volunteers into the emergency operational procedures.

Volunteers must have a clear role within the national and local system (G6.5-6), so it is required to define their roles and the chain of command to operate in a coordinated way with the other actors involved in a cross-border MCI. The integration of volunteers in the response can be done in two different ways:

- A pre-organisation integrated into the emergency plan, through NGOs and known volunteer organisations
- A spontaneous system through new volunteers integrated during the emergency
- Through the area's organizations (e.g., local firefighters, Civil Protection training of volunteers, etc.)

It would be good practice to include a crisis management expert from voluntary societies in the coordination of the response. This practice has proven effective in responses to recent floods, storms, heat waves, population movements, forest fires and man-made disasters. This expert can be included in local government bodies, to facilitate communication with several stakeholders.

OP6.5-3: Guarantee the involvement of volunteers in field exercises.

Regular joint exercises with the different actors involved during an emergency are essential, not only to test personal skills in a "real" environment, but also to train and test how the actors work together and to be able to improve and correct where necessary. Volunteers are part of the scenario and should be taken into account in joint exercises.

OP6.5-4: Ensure protection of volunteers during their operation exploring insurance field.

To ensure optimal protection of volunteers during their activity (G6.5-9), it is necessary to have adequate insurance. Many of the risks are known in advance and should be recorded and avoided. It would make sense to follow a strategic approach by defining a limited area of assistance as well as risk-free activities for those volunteers who are not protected by insurance.

OP6.5-5: Creation of a lessons learned database in Civil Protection.

The creation of a global lessons learned database with the standardised outcomes from debriefing reports (UCPM Lessons learned and Exchange of Experts programmes) would make easier to identify practices that could be institutionalised and procedures that requires corrective action to improve from past experiences the response and preparedness to cross-border MCI scenarios in Civil Protection. The development of such a database would promote

transparency and collective learning among countries, thereby strengthening preparedness and response at the global level.

OP6.5-6: Introduction of first aid spontaneous volunteers' management course/ programme.

In the large-scale disasters usually a large number of medical and non-medical staff volunteers are involved in order to support field operations. It is possible that different people with different skill and training can't collaborate. So far there is no unified training programme how to manage those people. It is important to start thinking and prepare a management course with adequate programme.

Gaps G6.5-3 and G6.5-5 are outside the project scope because they imply government involvement to develop adequate host country support structures and procedures to receive assistance from the UCPM and submitting assessments of risk and risk management capabilities to the European Commission to improve coordination and coherence between EU and national policies.

Similarly, to the gaps G6.5-3 and G6.5-5, Gap 6.5-8 regarding the insufficient legislation for volunteers is as well out of the VALKYRIES scope as it implies government action. Governments should do more to explore legal mechanisms to protect volunteers in emergencies.

Opportunities			
Civil Protection and Aid Volunteerism			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP6.5-1	G6.5-4 G6.5-14 G6.5-11	Encourage the intercultural competencies and foreign language skills in the training for first responders to cross-border MCI	To ensure compatibility and complementarity between intervention teams, the UCPM provides a training programme. The training helps experts improve their coordination and assessment skills in disaster response, but it should be complemented with the intercultural competencies and foreign language skills.
OP6.5-2	G6.5-6 G6.5-13	Integration of volunteers into the emergency operational procedures	Define the roles, "chain of command", liability and the way to operate within the emergency cycle for volunteers.
OP6.5-3	G6.5-7 G6.5-13	Guarantee the involvement of volunteers in field exercises	Field exercises test the specific response capabilities, self-sufficiency, interoperability, coordination and procedures of the different actors and their response material. The UCPM should ensure that volunteers participate in its field exercises, as they are one of the actors involved.
OP6.5-4	G6.5-9	Ensure protection of volunteers during their operation exploring insurance field.	Follow a strategic approach by defining a limited area of assistance as well as risk-free activities for those volunteers who are not protected by insurance.
OP6.5-5	G6.5-10	Creation of a lessons learned database in Civil Protection	A global database of lessons learned would make easier to connect outcomes from past

Opportunities			
Civil Protection and Aid Volunteerism			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
			that could be transformed into recommendations for future improvement.
OP6.5-6	G6.5-1 G6.5-2 G6.5-11 G6.5-12	Introduction of first aid spontaneous volunteers' management course/ programme	In the large-scale disasters usually a large number of medical and non-medical staff volunteers to support field operations. So far there is no unified training programme how to manage those people.

Table 10 – Opportunities from task civil protection and aid volunteerism

7. Conclusions

7.1. WP6 conclusion

In the course of the development of deliverable D6.2 and current update **D6.6**, the partners in the WP6 identified a total of **83 gaps and 57 opportunities**. In the process of the update, there were identified some overlaps and contradictions were resolved. The goal was to cluster the gaps and opportunities and to categorise them.

The following table shows the number of gaps and opportunities classified by WP6 tasks in which they are included.

	GAPS	OPPORTUNITIES	Total
T.6.1 Resource Federation and trusted information sharing	35	30	65
T6.2 Education and Training for first aid responses	22	9	31
T6.3 Raising practitioner and social awareness	8	6	14
T6.4 Civil-Military Cooperation	4	6	10
T6.5 Civil Protection and Aid Volunteerism	14	6	20
Total	83	57	140

Table 11 – Summary of gaps and opportunities found for WP6

7.2. Conclusions for Resource federation and trusted information sharing

Emergency scenarios at EU level require a high cooperation in different levels, where cross-border situations require capabilities for resource federation and trusted information sharing. This data sharing must be performed during a determined duration, ensuring data confidentiality, service and data integrity, and service and data availability. Additionally, frameworks offering this functionality is strongly required.

The analysis of current resource federation and trusted information sharing capabilities at EU level identifies multiple gaps or limitations that need to be taken into consideration. First, there is a lack of effective data federation strategies in cross-border scenarios. Moreover, current protocols and technologies for data confidentiality, integrity and availability are not sufficient to cover the requirements of these scenarios. Additionally, current frameworks are commonly developed to solve particular problems, and cannot be applied to broader contexts.

Based on these limitations, there is a huge margin for improvement concerning data federation in cross-sector, cross-hierarchical and cross-border scenarios. Based on that, there are great opportunities for creating new frameworks and improving existing technologies to improve confidentiality, availability and integrity issues.

7.3. Conclusions for Education and Training for first aid responses

The analyses made in the framework of the task T6.2 Education and training for first aid responses identified the following groups of gaps and needs at the EU and national levels.

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First, there is a need to standardise the E&T of first aid responders within the European MS and to create a common curriculum for Basic First Aid in emergency medicine to ensure a comparable knowledge base to provide equivalent services between the MS. Besides, there is a lack of standard for cross-border recognition of first aid courses in the EU. It is necessary to define minimum required competencies for training for MCI and disasters.

Second, paramedic training varies in European countries with regard to the level of training, the content of the courses, their length, etc. In the same time, there is a growing need for highly trained paramedics. Cross-border ICM cooperation requires paramedics to have comparable knowledge bases and to be able to provide equivalent services between countries.

Third, there is a lack of standardisation in the response to multi-victim incidents. Not all EU countries have a national standard operating procedure for the management of mass casualty incidents or disasters. In some cases, procedures exist at the regional level but there is no standardisation at the national level. Besides, emergency services have different ownership in EU countries (state, local communities, private). This situation makes the standardisation difficult in areas such as staff training, multi-agency education, research and development, etc. This lack of standardisation is a hindrance to cross-sectoral and cross-border cooperation. Moreover, there is a lack of cooperation and coordination between first aid responders and other crisis management institutions.

Fourth, one of the most important needs is related to the lack of certification in the training of medical first responders at national and the EU level to improve cross-border cooperation.

The fifth groups of gaps s related to the lack of enough resources for FAR in terms of staff composition of the emergency care teams (medical doctors, paramedics, emergency medical technicians or assistants etc.) and capacity of the FARs to use modern technologies; lack of a common, national picture of vehicles/ambulances.

Sixth, there is no lessons learned system at the EU level to collect, analyse and share information from simulations or real emergencies that can improve collective learning among countries or other stakeholders to strengthen the preparedness of FAR and other crisis management institutions joint response to cross-border emergencies.

Based on the analysis of the identified gaps and needs, the following harmonisation opportunities were identified.

First, the creation of a common core curriculum to be used as a basis for the implementation of emergency medicine as a speciality and the paramedic's training. The experience of the WHO that provides a classification and minimum standards for emergency medical teams serves as a basis for a European classification. Besides, the EU institution will have to work to establish a commonly valid European First Aid Certificate to guarantee the minimum knowledge base in first aid at the European level. The training to get this kind of certificate should be recognised via the European Qualification Framework and can be conducted by the European Agency for Health and Safety at Work, based on the guidelines of the European Resuscitation Council. Finally, there is a clear need to develop and test a joint, multinational shot training course to include not only basic skills for first aid response, but also GDPR issues, coordination and cooperation with other first responders, effective and secure data management, advanced technological tools that can help effective work of first responders in case of MCI, etc.

Second, the transformation of widely adopted national guidelines and procedures into standards would solve the cross-border interoperability issues and will help the adoption of common methodologies in general, and to common ways for the organisation of training exercises for first responders in particular.

Third, the creation of a Register of European First Aid members would allow the standardization of intervention protocols in Mass Casualty Incident, optimize the resources available in each country and improve coordination and cooperation among EU MS in case of cross-border incidents.

Fourth, adoption of the procedures use of modern tools for information exchange among FARs and other crisis management intuitions is vital to facilitate cross-sectoral and cross-border cooperation in case of MCI. To achieve this goal, the institutions must define the data that are relevant and necessary for management in their sphere of action. Standardising the data collected would facilitate the compilation of the information and its analysis to improve response and giving recommendations to decision-makers.

Fifth, the creation of a lessons learned database for FARs at the EU level with the standardised outcomes from debriefing reports would make easier to identify practices that could be institutionalised and procedures that requires corrective action to improve from past experiences the response and preparedness to cross-border MCI emergencies. Implementation of a system based on the EU Civil Protection Knowledge Network and Lessons Learned Programme or WHO Guidance for After Action Review.

Sixth, creating or supplementing the legislative framework in the field of natural disasters and environmental catastrophes is imperative from the point of view of refining the conceptual apparatus, because the declaration of a state of emergency requires the existence of a law defining extraordinary events.

7.4. Conclusions for Raising practitioner and social awareness

Within task T6.3 Raising practitioner and social awareness there have been 7 gaps and 7 opportunities related to gaps identified. Each gap generates an opportunity. Gaps, which have been identified, come either from literature or professional experience. 4 gaps out of 7 have been described as professional experience and come from real work and experience of first responders.

T6.3 refers to better practitioner and social awareness. When we take into consideration these terms, firstly there is a need for practitioners to have good and sufficient situational awareness and secondly there is a need for social awareness involving social media.

Both practitioner and social awareness require access to information about the incident location, the object(s) involved, the nature of the incident, its development, the dangers and risks, the people that are likely to be affected, and the existing, possible, and desirable actions to handle the incident. This information must be relevant, accurate, up to date, complete and available in an appropriate format and in real time to all those involved in managing the whole incident.

As it was pointed out either practitioner or social awareness need exchange of critical information among different first aid responder. This kind of information require real-time and true knowledge about any kind of incident. Firstly practitioners – first responders need to have COP and good situational awareness.

Communication has been an important aspect in disaster management and a part of information management. Inaccurate and/or incomplete information between agencies, between all involved first responders, between disaster managers and public, between countries (when we are taking cross-border incident into consideration) will cause a problem in communication which then leads to problems during disaster management. During a disaster or any kind of incident, it is necessary to improve response, especially in terms of communication and reporting lines.

Communication is essential and only via effective communication and communication channels each response to any kind of incident should be successful. Unifying of common language for several countries seems to be not possible, but a need for new common nomenclatures, indicative signs, warning systems or colour codes can solve this issue of misunderstanding. This can lead to better awareness immediately during the incident, where population needs to be informed very quickly.

Debriefing sessions have not been sufficient and there is a need for better post-incident debriefing sessions, for each agency of first responders separately and also this kind of sessions for all involved FRs agencies during disaster of MCI.

Last but not least, social media plays an important role during incidents. Social media tools are integrated in most parts of our daily lives, as citizens, netizens, researchers or emergency responders. SM tools may serve as an integral and significant component of crisis response.

Raising practitioner and social awareness remains still very challenging issue. Practitioners/first responders require real-time, visualized and quick information, to have a COP about the incident. Population also requires information about disaster or incident, nowadays social media are becoming an integral and significant component of crisis and emergency response.

7.5. Conclusions for Civil-Military cooperation

The comparative analysis of the disaster response systems and the normative base related to civil-military cooperation and interaction in conditions of large-scale disasters accompanied by mass casualties and destruction shows that there are significant differences in legislation, preparation, construction and principles of operation.

It is clear that issues related to civil-military cooperation in the process of providing assistance to the population under the Civil Protection Mechanism are currently generally complex, with a diverse legal framework, significant differences in the organization, preparation and management of forces and means involved in search and rescue in the disaster area.

In many countries there is a good legal framework and regulations for participation in various structures and organizations, including by law (Germany, Austria, Finland and Sweden). In other matters they are partially and relatively poorly regulated by by-laws - ordinances, orders or instructions of the head (Bulgaria, Slovakia).

Moreover, countries like these rely more on the assistance of the armed forces in case of emergency and for this reason the distribution of responsibilities and obligations for planning, preparing and managing the response is centralized and raised to higher levels of administrative structures (Bulgaria, Spain, Greece, and Denmark).

While in other countries, these issues are decentralized and assigned to territorial authorities (Finland, Germany, and Sweden). In these countries, the army and the armed forces in general

intervene only in exceptional cases, in disasters at the national or international level, as well as in threats to the security of the country from outside.

We can conclude that in most countries there are many different approaches to dealing with natural disasters and this is somewhat normal. But the problem is that there is a common lack of protocols, standards and programs for joint training and interaction between military structures and civilian actors in response of crises, natural disasters and catastrophes.

Thus, we need to develop some suggestions/possibilities for harmonisation on the preparedness and cross-sectorial collaboration for first aid response to multi-casualty disasters.

These possibilities/opportunities should be aimed for enhancing mutual capabilities in the prevention, preparedness and crises management process in the scope of cross-institutional cooperation.

7.6. Conclusions for Civil Protection and Aid Volunteerism

In T6.5 Civil Protection and Aid Volunteerism we identified 14 gaps and 6 opportunities related to gaps identified. Not all the gap identified generates an opportunity. Gaps was identified either from literature analysis or professional experience.

The main topic is about a coordinated emergency response. The various disaster management actors need to be aware of each other's systems and standard operating procedures. Integrated and cross sectorial training and exercises are useful to expand this knowledge.

In addition, successful coordination during cross-border MCI relies on shared operational procedures.

The creation of global lessons learned database with the standardised outcomes from debriefing reports would make easier to identify practices that could be institutionalised and procedures that require corrective action to improve the response to cross-border MCI scenarios in Civil Protection.

Volunteers and aid volunteerism organisation must have a clear role within the national and local system. It is mandatory to define their roles and the chain of command to operate in a coordinated way with the other actors involved in a cross-border MCI.

It would be good practice to include a crisis management expert from voluntary societies in the coordination of the response as demonstrated in recent MCI.

8. Annex A – References and bibliography

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9. Annex B – Glossary

Acronym	Description
AAR	After Action Review
AEM	Emergency Medical Ambulance
C&C	Command and Control
CECIS	Common Emergency Communication and Information System
CIMIC	Civil-Military Cooperation
COP	Common Operational Picture
DG ECHO	Directorate General for European Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations
DPPI SEE	Disaster preparedness and prevention initiative for southeast Europe
DRM	Disaster Risk Management
E&T	Education and Training
EDRI	European Emergency Disaster Response Information System
EKAV	Ethniko Kentro Amesis Voithias – Greece’s National Center for Emergency Care
EMC	European Medical Corps
EMC	The European Medical Corps
EMS	Emergency Medical Services
EMT	Emergency medical teams
EQF	European Qualification Framework
ERC	European Resuscitation Council
ERCC	Emergency Response Coordination Centre
EUAV	EU Aid Volunteers
EU-OSHA	European Agency for Health and Safety at Work
FARs	First Aid Responders
FRS	Fire and Rescue Service
FS	Fire Service
GFARC	Global First Aid Reference Centre
GSCP	General Secretariat of Civil Protection (in Greece)
IFRC	International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies
INEM	National Institute of Medical Emergency
MCI	Mass Casualty Incidents
MCI	Mass Causality Incidents
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
OCHA	United Nations Office for Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs
SM	Social media
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
TAS	Rescue Ambulance Crew
UCPM	EU Civil Protection Mechanism
UNDAC	United Nations Disaster Assessment and Coordination
VMER	Medical Vehicles of Emergency and Resuscitation
VOSTs	Virtual Operations Support Teams
WHO	World Health Organization

Table 12 – Glossary